

Systematic Review Protocol for the “Pathogens in Foods”

Database: Prevalence and Concentration of Main Biological Hazards in Food Matrices

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1. Main Objective of the Systematic Review

The main objective of the systematic review is to identify and extract, under a categorised arrangement, information and data on the occurrence (i.e., prevalence and concentration) of the most important biological hazards in various foods produced and marketed in Europe. Data periodically obtained from peer-reviewed articles will feed the web application *Pathogens in Foods* (<https://pif.esa.ipb.pt/>) through a dedicated database insertion system (<https://pathogens-in-food-frontend.vercel.app/>).

The biological hazards (foodborne pathogens) considered are: *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter*, Shiga-toxin producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia duodenalis*, Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus and Norovirus. The foods comprise beverages, meat and meat products, eggs and egg products, milk and dairy products, seafood, produce – fruits and vegetables, cereals and composite products.

The present systematic review protocol will be employed to retrieve published studies and data in the following periods:

Search of February 2023: Covering studies published between January 2022 and December 2022.

Search of August 2023: Covering studies published between January 2023 and July 2023.

Search of January 2024: Covering studies published between August 2023 and January 2024.

Search of August 2024: Covering studies published between January 2024 and July 2024.

Search of January 2025: Covering studies published between August 2024 and January 2025.

Search of August 2025: Covering studies published between January 2025 and July 2025.

Search of January 2026: Covering studies published between August 2025 and January 2026

The protocol employed to retrieve studies published between January 2000 and December 2021 can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7504196>¹. The primary studies whose data have been inserted in the Pathogens-in-Foods database and have been verified until 30 January 2023 are compiled in a BibTeX file of records².

2. Protocol for the Systematic Review

2.1 Review question

The review question is: “what is the occurrence (i.e., prevalence and/or concentration) of the most important biological hazards in the various foods and food products produced and/or commercialised in Europe?”. The review question is of a typical *descriptive* nature as it enquires about a condition of interest (i.e., contamination by foodborne pathogens) in a population of foods. This descriptive question has a simple PO (*population* and *outcome*) structure with key elements that can be broken down, as follows:

Population: Food products in general, namely, beverages, meat and meat products, eggs and egg products, milk and dairy products, seafood, produce – fruits and vegetables, cereals and composite products, produced and/or placed on the market in Europe.

Outcome: Occurrence of at least one of the following biological hazards, *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter*, Shiga-toxin producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia duodenalis*, Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus and Norovirus, expressed as either prevalence or concentration measured in the population.

Because both key elements can be clearly specified, the review question is *close-framed*, which is advantageous because it enables the setting of more clear eligibility criteria *a priori*, as opposed to open-framed questions.

¹ IPB/Anses. (2022). Systematic Review Protocol: Prevalence and Concentration of Main Biological Hazards in/on Food Matrices. Zenodo. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504196.

² IPB/Anses. (2023). BibTeX file of verified records in PIF. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7662845>

2.2 Criteria for inclusion of individual studies

For a study to be included in the systematic review, it should comply with criteria related to study characteristics (i.e., at the levels of study design and setting, population, outcomes of interest, and method used), and criteria related to report characteristics (i.e., type of publication and language of the full text). The eligibility criteria are described in Table 1.

Data in graphical format

The inclusion of a primary research study whose results are presented in graphical format will be decided on a case-by-case basis. It will depend on how feasible and reliable the extraction of data from the charts is.

Table 1: Eligibility criteria for inclusion of individual studies in the systematic review

Type of criteria	Eligibility criteria
<i>Criteria related to study characteristics</i>	
Study design and setting	[1] Occurrence data must originate from observational studies that could be cross-sectional or longitudinal where food units have been sampled by a randomised design, either simple or stratified. These designs are typically used in studies related to microbiological surveillance, microbiological characterisation of foods, and microbiological surveys on farms, in food factories, at retail or in restauration establishments.
Population	[2] Foods, as finished product or during production/processing, must be sampled from farms, processing facilities, retail or restauration establishments located in a European country. [3] Food chain stage where samples were taken must be specified.
Outcomes of interest	[4] Occurrence data must be given for any of the following 14 biological hazards: <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i> , Shiga-toxin producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> (STEC), <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> , <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , <i>Bacillus cereus</i> , <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> , <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp., <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> , Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus and Norovirus. [5] The study must present the results on prevalence and/or enumeration of the pathogen in/on foods. For prevalence, it should provide at least <i>sample size</i> and <i>number of positive samples</i> ; and for enumeration, it should provide at least the <i>sample size</i> , <i>a measure of concentration</i> , and in addition, for bacteria, it should provide or allow the calculation of the <i>limit of quantification</i> .

Method	[6] The microbiological method used must be indicated, or alternatively a reference provided; and the sample size must be higher than 3 units.
<i>Criteria related to report characteristics</i>	
Language of the full text	[7] English, Spanish, French, Portuguese
Publication type	[8] Primary research studies, reviews and systematic reviews

Examples of primary research studies excluded:

Primary research studies not meeting the pre-set criteria will not be included in the systematic review. Examples of primary research studies that will be excluded are: (1) reports of pathogens' counts from likely food vehicles within the context of investigation of foodborne outbreaks; (2) studies providing occurrence data without pointing out the microbiological method used or at least citing an informative source in the list of references; (3) studies that do not provide the amount of analytical sample used in the detection essay either directly in the methodology description or in the references; and (4) studies on serology prevalence of pathogens in live animals within the context of determining risk factors of pathogens in herds/flocks.

2.3 Searching for individual studies

The bibliographic search will be conducted using a combination of general terms, biological hazards, foodstuffs and countries.

General terms (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

“microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR “microbiological quality” OR “microbiological safety” OR analyses OR analysis OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR detection OR enumeration OR incidence OR investigation OR occurrence OR presence OR prevalence OR sampling OR survey

Biological hazards (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

Bacillus cereus OR “B. cereus” OR Clostridium perfringens OR “C. perfringens” OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR ((Escherichia coli OR “E. coli”) AND (pathogenic OR shiga* OR verocytotoxi* OR enterohaemorrhagic OR enterohemorrhagic OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)) OR Listeria monocytogenes OR “L. monocytogenes” OR Staphylococcus aureus OR “S. aureus” OR Yersinia enterocolitica OR “Y. enterocolitica” OR Campylobacter OR “C. jejuni” OR “C. coli” OR Salmonella OR Cryptosporidium OR “C. parvum” OR “C. hominis” OR Giardia OR “G. duodenalis” OR “Giardia intestinalis” OR “G. cuniculus” OR “G. meleagridis” OR “G. ubiquitum” OR “G. canis” OR “G. felis” OR “G. muris” OR “G. viatorum” OR

Toxoplasma OR “T. gondii” OR “hepatitis A” OR “hepatitis E” OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR norwalk.

Foods (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

Beverages:

water OR “soft drink*” OR beverage OR beverages OR coffee OR drink* OR juice* OR smoothie* OR soda* OR tea OR infusion

Meat:

meat* OR beef OR bovine OR cow OR veal OR swine OR pork OR piglet OR pig OR ewe OR lamb* OR mutton OR ovine OR sheep OR caprine OR goat* OR horse* OR broiler* OR chicken* OR duck* OR ostrich* OR poultry OR turkey* OR game OR deer OR fowl OR rabbit OR venison OR “wild boar” OR “cold cut*” OR “hot dog*” OR bacon OR bologna OR burger* OR charcuterie OR chorizo* OR deli* OR frankfurter* OR ham* OR hotdog* OR kidney OR liver OR meatball* OR nugget* OR offal OR paté OR pâté OR pate* OR pepperoni* OR salami* OR sausage* OR tongue OR pastrami OR salchichon OR mortadella OR baloney OR boloney OR polony OR terrine* OR rilette* OR steak

Eggs:

custard OR egg* OR yolk OR albumen

Dairy:

dairy OR “baby formula” OR “chocolate milk” OR “ice cream” OR “infant formula” OR “infant powder” OR “milk powder” OR butter OR buttermilk OR cheese* OR cream* OR curd* OR dessert* OR fat* OR ice-cream OR milk OR whey OR yoghurt* OR yogurt* OR colostrum OR feta OR brie OR camembert OR “queso blanco” OR chevre OR “blue-vein*” OR “mold ripe*” OR “mould ripe*” OR “Danish blue” OR gorgonzola OR roquefort OR ricotta OR mozzarella OR “dulce de leche” OR “crème fraiche” OR cheddar OR “Parmigiano Reggiano” OR “grana Padano”

Seafood:

seafood OR seafood* OR “sea food” OR “sea foods” OR “smoked fish” OR “cold smoked” OR “cold-smoked” OR “hot smoked” OR “hot-smoked” OR “dried fish” OR gravad OR graved OR gravlax OR “gravad lax” OR “marinated fish” OR “salted fish” OR anchov* OR clam* OR clams OR cockle* OR cod OR crab* OR crustacean* OR fish* OR halibut OR herring OR lobster* OR mackerel OR mollusc* OR mollusk* OR mussel* OR oyster* OR pollock OR prawn* OR salmon OR sardine OR scallop* OR shellfish OR shrimp* OR trout OR tuna OR hake OR crayfish OR bivalve* OR carp OR caviar OR squid OR cuttlefish OR cockle OR cockles OR snail OR eel OR sturgeon

- Vegetables:* vegetable* OR produce OR “germinated seed*” OR “green salad*” OR “leafy green” OR “leafy greens” OR “mixed salad*” OR “mixed vegetable*” OR “pre-cut salad*” OR “vegetable mix” OR fungi OR herb* OR lettuce OR mushroom* OR salad* OR spinach OR sprout* OR veggie* OR “raw produc*” OR “frozen produc*” OR microgreens OR avocado* OR salad* OR tomato* OR guacamole* OR taboulé OR pea OR peas OR bean OR beans OR chickpea* OR sprout* OR carrot OR carrots OR broccoli* OR beetroot* OR corn OR lentil* OR cucumber*
- Legumes:* legume* OR “dried seed*” OR “dry seed*” OR nut* OR oilseed* OR spice* OR pepper OR cinnamon OR turmeric OR cumin OR oregano OR nutmeg OR rosemary OR saffron OR basil OR garlic OR pulses OR almond OR sesame
- Grains:* grain* OR bakery OR bread* OR cake* OR cereal* OR confectionary OR flakes OR flour OR maize OR pastries OR pastry OR rice OR seed* OR wheat
- Fruits:* fruit* OR “fruit mix” OR “fruit salad” OR “mixed fruit” OR “sliced fruit” OR “stone fruit” OR berries OR berry OR citrus* OR drupe* OR pome* OR apple* OR banana* OR melon* OR peach*
- Oils and sugars:* fat OR oil* OR sugar* OR syrup* OR honey OR chocolate
- Composite:* meal OR meals OR food OR foods OR “buffet meal*” OR “complex food” OR “frozen meal*” OR multi-ingredient OR “multi ingredient” OR “probiotic drink*” OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR “ready meal” OR “ready prepared” OR “ready to eat” OR “sous vide” OR coleslaw OR composite* OR convenience OR cured OR dip OR dips OR dish OR dishes OR dressing* OR dumpling* OR fermented OR filling OR gravy OR hummus OR jam* OR kebab OR macerated OR marinad* OR marinate* OR mayonnaise OR pasta OR pizza OR pickled OR preserved OR pudding* OR puree* OR salsa OR salsas OR salted OR sandwich* OR sashimi OR ceviche OR sauce* OR smoked OR snack OR snacks OR soup OR soups OR stew* OR surimi OR sushi OR tofu* OR topping* OR vegan OR vegetarian OR chowder OR tahini
- Countries (Affiliation OR Title-Keywords-Abstract):* Albania OR Andorra OR Armenia OR Austria OR Azerbaijan OR Belarus OR Belgium OR Bosnia and Herzegovina OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark OR England OR Estonia

OR Finland OR France OR Georgia OR Germany OR Greece OR Hungary OR Iceland OR Ireland OR Italy OR Kazakhstan OR Kosovo OR Latvia OR Liechtenstein OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Macedonia OR Malta OR Moldova OR Monaco OR Montenegro OR Netherlands OR North Macedonia OR Norway OR Poland OR Portugal OR Romania OR Russia OR San Marino OR Serbia OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Scotland OR Spain OR Sweden OR Switzerland OR Turkey OR Ukraine OR United Kingdom OR UK OR Vatican OR Wales OR Yugoslavia OR Europe* OR EU

AND NOT Terms (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

“in vitro” OR “in-vitro” OR “challenge study” OR “essential oil*” OR antimicrobial* OR attribution OR biofilm* OR “plant extract” OR “extracts” OR feed OR livestock OR sanitiser OR sanitizer OR spiked OR “feed supplement*”

Articles will be searched in the e-bibliographic databases PubMed, Web of Science Core Collection, (Science Citation Index Expanded and Emerging Sources Citation Index), Scopus and SciELO (<https://scielo.org>) (see Annex 1), using the aforementioned terms duly connected (General terms AND Biological hazards AND Foodstuff AND Country AND NOT Selected terms) and in the proper database syntax. The entries will be filtered by database insertion date (according to the search periods specified in Section 1), type of publication (only primary research articles and reviews will be considered) and languages (English, Spanish, French and Portuguese³). Date of searches and number of records retrieved will be duly documented. The bibliographic search process in the four databases will be carried out by two researchers working in parallel and on the same day, who will then compare the number of records recovered, which should duly match in order to proceed with the next steps.

2.4 Deduplication of individual studies

The volume of bibliographic citations will be documented and managed in a project built on DistillerSR software, which will be set to identify duplicate references. Duplicates will be carefully checked and deleted/merged by the two researchers.

From the volume of deduplicated citations, reviews and systematic reviews will be identified; and their list of references will be downloaded to a separate project and filtered by a temporal boundary. The temporal boundary corresponds to the lapse from 2022 until the upper bound of the current search period. These “additional” references will be tagged, incorporated to the large volume of citations, and deduplicated. It is important that the additional records are differentiated from the others by tags, since this

³ Only these additional languages are considered for being the working languages of the IPB-Anses team.

is implemented as a mechanism of validation of the current search strings, and an opportunity to add missed citations.

Records for all foodborne pathogens will be kept in one single reference database. The reference databases will be managed by two senior experts in systematic reviews, who will ensure maintenance and updating of the databases at the different stages of the review process.

2.5 Selecting the individual studies

The whole process of selection of individual studies will be carried out by two trained reviewers and two senior reviewers. Once all the entries have been deduplicated, relevant studies will be screened for inclusion by one trained reviewer. In case a new staff member joins the project, training in SR and a pilot will be conducted by the senior reviewers. Doubts on the inclusion of a study will be resolved in the regular meetings with the senior reviewer(s). Three steps will be followed:

- a. *Title/abstract (Ti/Ab) screening.* Each of the titles and abstracts from the bibliographic databases will be screened for its relevance to answering the review question. The number of records that did not pass this first screening or remained unclear will be annotated.
- b. *Examining full-text reports.* Records that pass the Ti/Ab screening and those that remain unclear will undergo an examination at full-text level. Each full-text reference will be screened for eligibility based on record and study characteristics, according to the inclusion criteria outlined in Section 2.2. All annotations relative to the inclusion criteria, study characteristics and outcome data will be made in the environment of the DistillerSR project.
- c. *Identification of possible duplicate publications.* Because sometimes the same study is reported or partially reported in two or more articles, these situations must be carefully identified to avoid double-counting. Records likely to be linked to the same study will be marked in the DistillerSR project for posterior evaluation, in discussion with one of the senior reviewers. If the evaluation of results points towards the case of a duplicate publication, the linked records will be grouped and examined as one study unit.

Each stage of the study selection process will be well documented, in order to make it (re-)assessable. The number of studies eligible for inclusion will be annotated, while, for the studies excluded at the full-text report level, the reasons for exclusion will be provided. To register the flow of the number of literature records along the different phases of the systematic review, a PRISMA chart will be used. A PRISMA chart template can be found in Annex 2.

2.6 Assessing the methodological quality

Each eligible primary research study will undergo a quality assessment. The results of a study will be signalled as *having potential for bias* if there is any suspicious of:

- a. *Selection bias*: in situations where there is a suspicion that proper randomisation of the food units was not achieved. For instance, when sampling was undertaken in the context of a monitoring program/surveillance implemented after an outbreak, or microbiological analysis of food sampled at retail but close to the end of shelf life.
- b. *Aggregation bias* or *reporting bias*: Prevalence or enumeration results are combined for distinct food classes within the same food category (for instance: prevalence data combined for pasteurised milk cheese and raw milk cheese; microbial concentrations pooled for raw sausage and fermented sausage) or combined for samples from different food chain stages (for instance: prevalence data combined for non-filleted and filleted fish).
- c. *Detection bias*: The outcomes of a study will be signalled as being potentially biased if any of the following two situations arises:
 - c1. Detection and/or quantification of the biological hazard is not undertaken using an approved or known microbiological method, or it is carried out using a newly proposed method. However, potential for bias should not be assigned if the study that proposes a new method provides an indication of the limit of detection or of test accuracy in comparison to a gold standard.
 - c2. Amount (weight, volume, surface or whole unit) of the analytical sample is not explicitly indicated in the study, but assumed from authors' previous publications, from the range of analytical sample amount provided in the text or taken from manufacturer's instructions in case a kit was used.
- d. *Quality of reporting*: In cases of lack of concordance between results presented in the text and those compiled in the table(s), the ones presented in tabular format will be taken, and the results marked as potentially biased.

The results taken from studies that present at least one of the aforementioned validity threats will be marked as potentially biased, in order to perform sensitivity analysis at a later stage during meta-analysis. Meeting more than one potential-for-bias criterion will not be considered sufficient to discard a study. Every study will undergo quality assessment by one reviewer, who, when in doubt, will consult with the second reviewer. Where there is no consensus, the senior reviewer(s) will resolve doubts on methodological quality assessment, and furthermore they will corroborate the correctness of the status of those studies marked as being potentially biased.

2.7 Data extraction from primary research studies

The collection of data from the primary research studies has been standardised according to the type of biological hazard, this is, bacteria, parasites and viruses. Therefore, there are three different data models built on the Pathogens-in-Foods

database. However, regardless of the type of pathogen, the data to be extracted are related to (i) general framing of the study, (ii) study characteristics relevant to explain heterogeneity in the outcomes; namely the nature of the food sampled and the method of detection/quantification, and (iii) outcome measures, detection and/or quantification.

Information relative to the occurrence of pathogens in foods will be inserted directly onto the Pathogens-in-Foods database. The fields to be completed are described below. Whenever applicable, the correspondence in metadata between PIF' variables and the EFSA's aggregated prevalence data models, except for the food description matrix, are explained in detail.

2.7.1 General framing data

The general framing data are common to bacteria, parasites and viruses, since they pertain to characteristics of the individual study.

Study ID: Unique identifier of the study. StudyID follows the rule: "FirstAuthorSurname_AbbreviatedJournal_PublicationYear".

Study type: (a) Survey, for studies whose objective was to characterise or investigate the microbiological safety of food, or its compliance to legislation; (b) Comparison, for studies comparing methods of detection of pathogens; and (c) Other, for any other type of study.

Country of publication: country of the institutional address of the corresponding author.

Year: starting year of the sampling.

Study duration: duration of the sampling in months.

2.7.2 Study characteristics data

The following study characteristics describe the food sample, and therefore, they are common to bacteria, parasites and viruses.

Country of sampling (ex. Food origin): country where the food was sampled.

Country of origin: country of production/processing of the food if stated in the study as different from the country of sampling.

For "Country of sampling" and "Country of origin", EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 8.0 Country, Country

All classes (countries) are correspondent, except for the following:

PIF Food origin	EFSA terminology		
	Code	Name	Observations
UK	GB	United Kingdom	
Northern Ireland	XI	United Kingdom (Northern Ireland)	
Wales	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned
WestEurope	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned
EastEurope	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned
NorthEurope	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned
SouthEurope	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned
CentralEurope	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned
Multiple	-	-	PIF term to be kept with no code assigned

Packaged status: (a) Yes, for samples of food in any type of packaging. If food is packaged, the class “In air”, “In modified atmosphere”, “Vacuum-packing” or “Unknown packaging material” should be selected to indicate normal atmosphere package, modified atmosphere package, vacuum package or other type of packaging, respectively; (b) No, for food samples without packaging, (c) Various, for samples of food that were both packaged and unpackaged, and (d) NA (not available), when the study does not indicate the packaging status of the food or cannot be reasonably deduced.

EFSA Catalogue, hierarchy and Facet: 14.1 MTX (FoodEx2 Matrix), Zoonoses hierarchy, Facets #19 (packaging material), #6 (surrounding medium) and #28 (process)

PIF Packaged status (old)	PIF Packaged status (new)	EFSA terminology		
		Code	Name	Observations
Yes	Yes	#F19.A18PV		String to be added to MTX code of the food.
	→In air	#F06.A0BA5	As in facet	
	→In modified atmosphere	#F06.A0BA6	As in facet	
	→Vacuum-packing	#F28.A07JK	As in facet	
	→Unknown packaging material	#F19.A18PV	As in facet	
No	No	-		No action taken
Various	Various	-		No action taken
NA	NA	-		No action taken

Sampling stage (ex. Stage): refers to the stage of the food chain from which the sample was extracted: (a) Farm, entailing any stage within primary production, (b) Mid-processing, including any processing stage within the reception of raw materials and the end of processing, (c) End-processing, when food products are sampled at the end of production, (d) Retail, when food products are sampled at any retail establishment or vending machines, and (e) Restauration, when sampling is carried out at restaurants or catering services.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 9.1 SAMPNT, zooss

PIF Stage	EFSA terminology		
	Code	Name	Observations
Farm	E100A →E101A	Primary production →Farm	See the new hierarchy for “Sampling stage” in the diagram below
MidProcessing	E300A	Manufacturing	
EndProcessing	E500A →E700A	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale →Storage	
Retail	E500A →E520A	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale →Retail	
Restauration	E500A →E910A	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale →Restaurant	

Temperature at retail: refers to the temperature class of the food when sampled: (a) Ambient temperature, (b) Chill, (c) Frozen, (d) Various, and (e) Not available.

RTE status: refers to whether the food produced or being produced is ready-to-eat (Yes) or non-ready-to-eat (No).

EFSA Catalogue, hierarchy and Facet: 14.1 MTX (FoodEx2 Matrix), Zoonoses hierarchy, Facet #24 (Intended use)

PIF RTE status	EFSA terminology		
	Code	Name	Observations
Yes	#F24.A07VP	-	String to be added to MTX code of the food
No	#F24.A07VQ	-	String to be added to MTX code of the food

Food label: is the description of the food sample as indicated in the study.

2.7.2.1 *Study characteristics for bacteria*

The following study characteristics are specific to bacteria.

Zoonotic agent (ex. Agent): refers to any of the 8 foodborne bacterial pathogens.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 14.3 PARAM, microParam

PIF Stage	EFSA terminology		
	Code	Name	Observations
Bacillus	RF-00000006-MCG	Bacillus cereus	
Campy	RF-00000042-MCG	Campylobacter	
Clostridium	RF-00000082-MCG	Clostridium perfringens	
Listeria	RF-00000251-MCG	Listeria monocytogenes	
Salmonella	RF-00000304-MCG	Salmonella	
Staphy	RF-00003852-MCG	Staphylococcus aureus	
STEC	RF-00000132-MCG	Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC)	
Yersinia	RF-00002538-MCG	Yersinia enterocolitica	

Serotype/serovar/other: refers to the serotype, serovar or any other distinct variation within a pathogenic bacterium. It is an open field.

Type of essay: (a) Detection, when the objective of the study is to investigate the presence or absence of the pathogen in/on the food samples; (b) Enumeration, when the objective of the study is to quantify the concentration of the pathogen in/on the food samples, and in the particular case of bacteria, when they are determined with no enrichment step; and (c) Both, when the study investigates both detection and quantification of pathogens in/on the food samples.

Detection essay type and **Detection essay**: Refers to the type of essay carried out for prevalence (culture, molecular, immunological, other), and more specifically, the detection essay. The detection essays within type of essay depend on the bacteria selected. Such a tree, called Detection methods' tree, is tabulated in Annex 3.

Enumeration essay type and **Enumeration essay**: Refers to the type of essay carried out for enumeration (culture, molecular, other), and more specifically, the enumeration essay. The enumeration essays within type of essay depend on the bacteria selected. Such a tree, called Enumeration methods' tree, is tabulated in Annex 3.

The variables **Detection essay** and **Enumeration essay** corresponds to the data element "Analytical method" of the aggregated prevalence data model, associated with the catalogue "ANLYMD", hierarchy "prvam". Nonetheless, only the standardised methods of PIF will be harmonized to those of EFSA's catalogue.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 11.0 ANLYMD, prvam, ANLYMD, fboam

Agent	PIF Detection/ Enumeration essay	EFSA terminology	
		Code	Name
Bacillus cereus	ISO 7932:2004	F176A	ISO 7932:2004 Bacillus cereus
	-	F176A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 7932:2004/Amd 1:2020 (Bacillus cereus) Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of presumptive Bacillus cereus — Colony-count technique at 30 degrees C — Amendment 1: Inclusion of optional tests
	-	F744A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	NMKL 67, 2021, 8th ed. (Bacillus cereus) Presumptive Bacillus cereus. Determination in foods. NMKL 67, 2021, 8th ed. Presumptive Bacillus cereus. Determination in foods.
	-	F744A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	NMKL 67, 2021, 8th ed. (Bacillus cereus) Presumptive Bacillus cereus. Determination in foods.
Campylobacter	-	F617A	ISO 10272-1:2017 Campylobacter
	-	F616A	ISO 10272-2:2017 Campylobacter
	NMKL 119	F600A	NMKL 119, 2007, 3rd Ed. Termotolerante Campylobacter
	-	F718A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 17995:2019 (Campylobacter) Water quality — Detection and enumeration of thermotolerant Campylobacter spp
Clostridium perfringens	ISO 7937:2004	F721A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 7937:2004 (Clostridium perfringens) Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of Clostridium perfringens — Colony-count technique
	-	To be provided	ISO 15213-1:2023. Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Clostridium

			spp. — Part 1: Enumeration of sulfite-reducing Clostridium spp. by colony-count technique
	-	F722A	ISO/DIS 15213-2 (Clostridium perfringens) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Clostridium spp. — Part 2: Enumeration of Clostridium perfringens by colony-count technique
	-	F781A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO/CD TS 15213-3 (Clostridium perfringens) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Clostridium spp. — Part 3: Detection of Clostridium perfringens
	-	F720A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 14189:2013 (Clostridium perfringens) Water quality — Enumeration of Clostridium perfringens — Method using membrane filtration
	-	F748A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	NMKL 95, 2009, 5th ed. (Clostridium perfringens) Clostridium perfringens. Determination in foods, feed and environmental samples.
Listeria monocytogenes	ISO 11290-1	F610A	ISO 11290-1:2017 Listeria
	ISO 11290-2	F611A	ISO 11290-2:2017 Listeria
	ISO 11290-1:2004	F169A	ISO 11290-1:1996/Amd 1:2004 Listeria
	ISO 11290-2:2004	F170A	ISO 11290-2:1998/Amd 1:2004 Listeria
	NMKL 136	F649A	NMKL 136, 5th ed. 2010, Listeria monocytogenes
Salmonella	ISO 6579:2002	-	ISO 6579:2002 Salmonella
	ISO 6579:2007	-	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007 (Annex D of ISO 6579) Salmonella
	-	F609A	ISO 6579-1:2017 Salmonella
	-	F783A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 6579-1:2017/Amd 1:2020 (Salmonella) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella — Part 1: Detection of Salmonella spp.
	-	F784A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO/TS 6579-2:2012 (Salmonella) Microbiology of food and animal feed — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella — Part 2
	-	F785A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO/TR 6579-3:2014 (Salmonella) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella — Part 3
	NMKL 71	F140A	NMKL 71, 1999, 5th Ed. Salmonella
	-	F601A	NMKL 187, 2007 Salmonella

	-	F753A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	NMKL 187, 2018, 3rd ed. (Salmonella) Salmonella. Detection in foods, animal faeces and environmental materials from primary animal production using MSRV (2018)
	-	F730A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 19250:2010 (Salmonella) Water quality — Detection of Salmonella spp. ISO 19250:2010 Water quality — Detection of Salmonella spp.
Staphylococcus aureus	ISO 6888-1:2003	F171A	EN ISO 6888-1:1999/Amdt 1:2003 Coagulase-positives staphylococci
	ISO 6888-2:2003	F172A	EN ISO 6888-2:1999/Amdt 1:2003 Coagulase-positives staphylococci
	-	F732A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 6888-1:2021 (Staphylococci) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (Staphylococcus aureus and other species) — Part 1: Method using Baird-Parker agar medium
	-	F733A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 6888-2:2021 (Staphylococci) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (Staphylococcus aureus and other species) — Part 2: Method using rabbit plasma fibrinogen agar medium
	-	F734A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 6888-3:2003 (Staphylococci) Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (Staphylococcus aureus and other species) — Part 3: Detection and MPN technique for low numbers
	-	F735A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 6888-1:2021/DAMD 1 (Staphylococci) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (Staphylococcus aureus and other species) — Part 1: Method using Baird-Parker agar medium — Amendment 1: Corrections
	-	F736A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO 6888-2:2021/DAMD 1 (Staphylococci) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (Staphylococcus aureus and other species) — Part 2: Method using rabbit plasma fibrinogen agar medium — Amendment 1: Corrections
	NMKL 66	F757A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD,	NMKL 66, 2009, 5th ed. (Staphylococci) Coagulase positive staphylococci. Enumeration in foods.

		fboam)	
Shiga toxin producing Escherichia coli	ISO 16654:2001	F593A	ISO 16654:2001 or NMKL 164:2005 or DIN 10167
	ISO/TS 13136:2012	F173A	ISO/TS 13136:2012 (including the EU-RL adaptation for O104:H4)
	-	F737A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO/CD 13136-1 (STEC) Microbiology of the food chain — Detection, isolation and characterization of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) — Part 1: Horizontal method for the detection and isolation of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC)
	-	F788A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO/CD 13136-2 (STEC) Microbiology of the food chain — Detection, isolation and characterization of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) — Part 2: Horizontal method for the characterization of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) isolates
	-	F695A	AFNOR BIO 12/25 05/09, ELFA method for E. coli O157
	-	F139A	NMKL 164, 2005, 2nd Ed. Escherichia coli O157
Yersinia enterocolitica	-	F618A	ISO 10273:2017 Yersinia enterocolitica
	-	F741A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	ISO/TS 18867:2015 (Yersinia enterocolitica & pseudotuberculosis) Microbiology of the food chain — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — Detection of pathogenic Yersinia enterocolitica and Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
	-	F759A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	NMKL 117, 1996, 3rd ed. (Yersinia enterocolitica) Yersinia enterocolitica. Detection in foods.
	NMKL 163	F760A (only in hierarchy ANLYMD, fboam)	NMKL 163, 2013, 2nd ed. (Yersinia enterocolitica & pseudotuberculosis) Pathogenic Yersinia enterocolitica and Yersinia pseudotuberculosis – real-time PCR methods for detection in food, feed and environmental samples.

Type of food: **Type of food:** the food will be categorised utilising a hierarchy system existing in the PIF database composed of a maximum of four variables: category, subcategory, class and subclass (specie or heat-treated status). Annex 4 compiles the food categorisation system for bacteria implemented in the PIF database. A parallel food categorisation system that maximises alignment with FoodEx2 catalogue will be implemented.

The food categorisation system of PIF database will be mapped to MTX (FoodEx2 Matrix) catalogue, taking advantage as much as possible of the available facets. For each constructed FoodEx2 coding, it will be checked whether it is present in the mapping file 2022_ZOO_CAT_MATRIX_FOODEx2_mapping.xlsx.

Organ sampled: When the sample is fish, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: skin, eyes, buccal cavity, gills, corporal cavity, liver, gonads, stomach, bowel, fillets and N/S. When the sample is meat extracted at the stage of mid-processing, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: diaphragm, meat juice, liver, heart, brain or blood.

2.7.2.2 *Study characteristics for viruses*

The following study characteristics are specific to viruses.

Zoonotic agent (ex. Virus): refers to any of the three viruses implemented in the database: Hepatitis A (HAV), Hepatitis E (HEV) or Norovirus.

Genotype: The genotype is a characteristic specific to HAV and HEV. For HAV, the genotype classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV and GVI; whereas for HEV, the genotype classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV, GVI and GVII.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 14.5 PARAM, microParam

PIF Agent	Genotype	EFSA terminology	
		Code	Name
Hepatitis A (HAV)		RF-00000230-MCG	Hepatovirus A
	GI	→RF-00013116-PAR	→Hepatovirus A GI
	II	→RF-00013117-PAR	→Hepatovirus A GII
	III	→RF-00013118-PAR	→Hepatovirus A GIII
	IV	-	
	V	-	
	VI	-	
Hepatitis E (HEV)		RF-00003091-PAR	Orthohepevirus A
	GI	→RF-00013081-PAR	→Orthohepevirus A G1
	II	→RF-00013082-PAR	→Orthohepevirus A G2
	III	→RF-00013083-PAR	→Orthohepevirus A G3
	IV	→RF-00013084-PAR	→Orthohepevirus A G4
	V	-	-
	VI	-	-
	VII	-	-
Norovirus		RF-00000041-MCG	Norovirus
	GI	→RF-00003060-PAR	Norovirus
	II	→RF-00003061-PAR	Norovirus
	III...GX	-	-

Subgenotype: The subgenotype is a characteristic specific to HAV and HEV. For HAV, the classes are A and B; whereas for HEV, the classes are A, B, C, D, E, F and G.

Subtype old genogroup: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the old genogroup classification. The classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV, GVI, GVII and GVIII.

Subtype old genotype: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the old genotype classification. The classes go from 1 to 25.

Subtype new genogroup: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the new genogroup classification. The classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV, GVI, GVII, GVIII, GIX and GX.

Subtype new genotype: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the new genotype classification. The classes go from 1 to 49.

Agent label: It is the description of the virus as indicated in the study.

Type of essay: (a) Prevalence, when the objective of the study is to investigate the presence or absence of the virus in/on the food samples; (b) Prevalence and Enumeration, when the objective of the study is, in addition, to quantify the concentration of the virus the food samples.

Detection essay type and Detection essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for prevalence (molecular, immunological, other), and more specifically, the detection essay. The detection essays within type of essay depend on the virus selected. Such a tree, called Detection methods' tree, is tabulated in Annex 5.

Enumeration essay type and Enumeration essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for enumeration (qPCR, reverse transcription-LAMP, digital PCR RT-qPCR, multiplex RT-qPCR, PCR-NPP, other), and more specifically, the enumeration essay. The enumeration essays within type of essay depend on the virus selected. Such a tree, called Enumeration methods' tree, is tabulated in Annex 5.

The variables **Detection essay** and **Enumeration essay** corresponds to the data element "Analytical method" of the aggregated prevalence data model, associated with the catalogue "ANLYMD", hierarchy "prvam". Nonetheless, only the standardized methods of PIF will be harmonized to those of EFSA's catalogue.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 11.0 ANLYMD, prvam, ANLYMD or fboam

Agent	PIF Detection/Enumeration essay	EFSA terminology	
		Code	Name
Hepatitis A	ISO 15216:2017	F619A	ISO 15216-1:2017 Hepatitis A virus and norovirus
	ISO/TS 15216:2013	F686A	ISO 15216-2:2013 Hepatitis A virus and norovirus
	-	F728A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD)	ISO 15216-1:2017/Amd 1:2021 (Hepatitis A & norovirus) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for

		or fboam)	determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 1: Method for quantification — Amendment 1
	ISO 15216:2019	F729A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD or fboam)	ISO 15216-2:2019 (Hepatitis A & norovirus) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 2: Method for detection
Norovirus	ISO 15216:2017	F619A	ISO 15216-1:2017 Hepatitis A virus and norovirus
	ISO/TS 15216:2013	F686A	ISO 15216-2:2013 Hepatitis A virus and norovirus
	-	F728A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD or fboam)	ISO 15216-1:2017/Amd 1:2021 (Hepatitis A & norovirus) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 1: Method for quantification — Amendment 1
	ISO 15216:2019	F729A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD or fboam)	ISO 15216-2:2019 (Hepatitis A & norovirus) Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 2: Method for detection

Essay identification: Refers to the type of essay carried out for virus identification, in case such an essay was done. Classes are: WGS, NGS, Other for the three viruses.

Essay infectivity: Refers to the type of essay carried out to determine the infectivity of the virus, and it is dependent on the virus. The Infectivity tree is tabulated in Annex 5.

Type of food: the food is categorised utilising the same hierarchy system as that of bacteria, comprising: category, subcategory, class and subclass (see Annex 4).

The food categorisation system of PIF database will be mapped to MTX (FoodEx2 Matrix) catalogue, taking advantage as much as possible of the available facets. For each constructed FoodEx2 coding, it will be checked whether it is present in the mapping file 2022_ZOO_CAT_MATRIX_FOODEx2_mapping.xlsx.

Organ sampled: When the sample is fish, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: skin, eyes, buccal cavity, gills, corporal cavity, liver, gonads, stomach, bowel, fillets and N/S. When the sample is meat extracted at the stage of mid-processing, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: diaphragm, meat juice, liver, heart, brain or blood.

2.7.2.3 Study characteristics for parasites

The following study characteristics are specific to parasites.

Zoonotic agent (ex. Parasite): refers to any of the three genus of parasites implemented in the database: *Toxoplasma*, *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium*.

Specie: refers to the specie of the parasite. For *Toxoplasma*, the species are: *gondi* and spp.; for *Giardia*, the species are *duodenalis* and spp.; and for *Cryptosporidium*, the species are: *parvum*, *hominis*, *meleagridis*, *ubiquitum*, *canis*, *cuniculus*, *felis*, *muris*, *viatorum*, spp., and other.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 14.5 PARAM, microParam

PIF Agent	Specie	EFSA terminology	
		Code	Name
Toxoplasma		RF-00002512-MCG	Toxoplasma
	spp.	RF-00002512-MCG	Toxoplasma
	<i>gondii</i>	→RF-00002514-MCG	→Toxoplasma <i>gondii</i>
Giardia		RF-00000226-MCG	Giardia
	<i>duodenalis</i>	→RF-00000227-MCG	→Giardia <i>intestinalis</i>
	spp.	→RF-00000228-MCG	→Giardia, unspecified sp.
Cryptosporidium		RF-00000086-MCG	Cryptosporidium
	<i>parvum</i>	→RF-00000088-MCG	→Cryptosporidium <i>parvum</i>
	<i>hominis</i>	→RF-00004098-MCG	→Cryptosporidium <i>hominis</i>
	<i>meleagridis</i>	→RF-00013637-PAR	→Cryptosporidium <i>meleagridis</i>
	<i>ubiquitum</i>	→RF-00013638-PAR	→Cryptosporidium <i>ubiquitum</i>
	<i>canis</i>	→RF-00013639-PAR	→Cryptosporidium <i>canis</i>
	<i>felis</i>	→RF-00013640-PAR	→Cryptosporidium <i>felis</i>
	<i>muris</i>	→RF-00013641-PAR	→Cryptosporidium <i>muris</i>
	<i>viatorum</i>	→RF-00013642-PAR	→Cryptosporidium <i>viatorum</i>
	others	→RF-00000087-MCG	→Cryptosporidium, unspecified, sp.

Subtype new: This variable is specific to *Toxoplasma* and *Giardia*, and refers to the subtype information according to the new classification. The new subtypes for *Toxoplasma* are: GI, GII, GIII, atypical and mixed; whereas the new subtypes for *Giardia* are: assemblages A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H and mixed.

Subtype old: This variable is specific to *Toxoplasma* and *Giardia*, and refers to the subtype information according to the old classification. The old subtypes for *Toxoplasma* are: Clade A, B, C, D, E, F and mixed; whereas the old subtypes for *Giardia* are: *enteritica*, *canis*, *bovis*, *cati*, *simondi*, *duodenalis*, and *psittaci*.

Custom subtype: refers to the subtype of *Cryptosporidium*.

Parasite label: It is the description of the parasite as indicated in the study.

Essay sample preparation: This variable stored the type of sample preparation prior to analysis, and it is conditional to the parasite selected. Such a tree, called Sample preparation tree, is tabulated in Annex 6.

Type of essay: (a) Prevalence, when the objective of the study is to investigate the presence or absence of the parasite in the samples; (b) Enumeration, when the objective of the study is to quantify the concentration of the parasite in the samples; and (c) Both, when prevalence and enumeration essays were carried out in the samples.

Detection essay type and Detection essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for prevalence (immunological, microscopy, molecular, reference methods, other), and more specifically, the detection essay. The detection essays within type of essay depend on the parasite selected. Such a tree, called Detection methods' tree, is tabulated in Annex 6.

Enumeration essay type and Enumeration essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for enumeration (immunological, microscopy, molecular, reference methods, other), and more specifically, the enumeration essay. The enumeration essays within type of essay depend on the parasite selected. Such a tree, called Enumeration methods' tree, is tabulated in Annex 6.

The variables **Detection essay** and **Enumeration essay** corresponds to the data element "Analytical method" of the aggregated prevalence data model, associated with the catalogue "ANLYMD", hierarchy "prvam". Nonetheless, only the standardized methods of PIF will be harmonized to those of EFSA's catalogue.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 11.0 ANLYMD, prvam, ANLYMD or fboam

Agent	PIF Detection/Enumeration essay	EFSA terminology	
		Code	Name
Cryptosporidium	ISO 18744 (2016)	F782A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD or fboam)	ISO 18744:2016 (Cryptosporidium & Giardia) Microbiology of the food chain — Detection and enumeration of Cryptosporidium and Giardia in fresh leafy green vegetables and berry fruits
	ISO 15553 (2006)	F723A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD or fboam)	ISO 15553:2006 (Cryptosporidium & Giardia) Water quality - Isolation and identification of Cryptosporidium oocysts and Giardia cysts from water ISO 15553:2006 Water quality — Isolation and identification of Cryptosporidium oocysts and Giardia cysts from water
Giardia	ISO 18744:2016 (IMS+IFM) (produce) : Centrifugation +IMS-CG+IFA	F782A (only in hierarchies ANLYMD or fboam)	ISO 18744:2016 (Cryptosporidium & Giardia) Microbiology of the food chain — Detection and enumeration of Cryptosporidium and Giardia in fresh leafy green vegetables and berry fruits
Giardia	ISO 15553: 2006 (water)	F723A (only in hierarchies)	ISO 15553:2006 (Cryptosporidium & Giardia) Water quality - Isolation and identification of

		ANLYMD or fboam)	Cryptosporidium oocysts and Giardia cysts from water ISO 15553:2006 Water quality — Isolation and identification of Cryptosporidium oocysts and Giardia cysts from water
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Essay identification type: Refers to the type of essay carried out for identification of the parasite (molecular, enzymatic, other), and the classes depend on the parasite. Such a tree, called Identification methods’ tree, is tabulated in Annex 6.

Essay infectivity type: Refers to the type of essay carried out to determine the infectivity of the parasite, and it is dependent on the parasite. The Infectivity tree is tabulated in Annex 6.

Type of food: the food is categorised utilising the same hierarchy system as that of bacteria, comprising: category, subcategory, class and subclass (see Annex 4).

Organ sampled: When the sample is fish, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: skin, eyes, buccal cavity, gills, corporal cavity, liver, gonads, stomach, bowel, fillets and N/S. When the sample is meat extracted at the stage of mid-processing, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: diaphragm, meat juice, liver, heart, brain or blood.

2.7.3 Outcome data

2.7.3.1 Outcome data for bacteria

The outcome data for bacteria is of three types: general results, prevalence results and enumeration results.

General results

Sample weight unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) cm², or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit, for instance, one strawberry subject to analysis.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 7.0 UNIT, smpwghUn

PIF Sample weight unit	EFSA terminology	
	Code	Name
g	G148A	g
ml	G156A	ml
cm2	G090A	cm ²
unit	-	unit

Total units tested (ex. Number of samples): refers to the number of samples submitted for analysis. It corresponds to the metrics of EFSA data models “Total units tested”.

Confirmation: It refers as to whether the detected or enumerated pathogen was subjected to confirmation (Yes) or not (No). When no information is provided, the class NA is used.

Number of samples with isolated strains: Refers to the number of samples with at least one isolated strain.

Bias potential: according to the assessment of methodological quality (Section 2.6), results are marked as potentially biased (1) or not (0).

Reason: If results are marked as potentially biased, the reason must be given.

Comments: Any comments relevant for internal validation assessment.

Prevalence results

Sample weight detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the detection essay.

Limit of detection (LoD): limit of detection of the method if given in the study in log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Detected samples: number of positives samples; and in the case of bacteria, necessarily after enrichment.

Enumeration results

Sample weight enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration essay.

Limit of quantification (LoQ): limit of quantification of the enumeration essay in log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Greater LoQ: number of “positive” samples (greater than the LoQ).

Lower LoQ: number of “negative” samples (lower than the LoQ).

[LoQ – 1]: number of samples whose counts are between LoQ and 1 log CFU per g, ml or cm², if LoQ is lower than 1 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[LoQ/1 – 2]: number of samples whose counts are between LoQ and 2 log CFU per g, ml or cm², if LoQ is between 1 and 2 log CFU per g, ml or cm²; or number of samples whose counts are between 1 and 2 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[2 – 3]: number of samples whose counts are between 2 and 3 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[3 – 4]: number of samples whose counts are between 3 and 4 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[4 – 5]: number of samples whose counts are between 4 and 5 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[5 – 6]: number of samples whose counts are between 5 and 6 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[6 – 7]: number of samples whose counts are between 6 and 7 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[7 – 8]: number of samples whose counts are between 7 and 8 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the pathogen in the samples, in log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Standard deviation: standard deviation of the concentration of the pathogen in the samples, in log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Counts model: refers to the approach used to estimate the mean concentration: (a) Impute, if the LoQ value was imputed to the non-detected samples to calculate the mean, or (b) Positive counts, if the mean was calculated using only the detected samples.

Counts vector {C₁, ..., C₉}: a vector of concentrations of the pathogen measured in a maximum of nine individual samples.

Maximum: refers to the maximum concentration enumerated in a positive sample in log CFU per g, ml or cm².

2.7.3.2 Outcome data for viruses

The outcome data is for viruses of three types: prevalence results, enumeration results, infectivity results and quality of molecular method.

Prevalence results

Sample weight unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) L, or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit, for instance, one strawberry subject to analysis.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 7.0 UNIT, smpwghUn

PIF Sample weight unit	EFSA terminology	
	Code	Name
g	G148A	g
ml	G156A	ml
L	-	L
unit	-	unit

Sample weight detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the detection essay.

Total units tested (ex. Number of samples): refers to the number of samples submitted for analysis. It corresponds to the metrics of EFSA data models “Total units tested”.

Detected: refers to the number of positive samples.

Are results corrected for extraction/recovery? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Are results given after drying? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Bias potential: according to the assessment of methodological quality (Section 2.6), results are marked as potentially biased (1) or not (0).

Reason: If results are marked as potentially biased, the reason must be given.

Comments: Any comments relevant for internal validation assessment.

Enumeration results

Sample weight enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration essay.

Counts unit: It is the unit in which the counts are given: raw genome copies per sample weight unit, log base 10 of the genome copies per sample weight unit, or natural logarithm of the genome copies per sample weight unit

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the virus in the samples in the unit specified

Standard deviation: mean concentration of the virus in the samples in the unit specified

Counts vector $\{C_1, \dots, C_9\}$: a vector of concentrations of the virus mean concentration of the virus in the unit specified, measured in a maximum of nine individual samples.

Minimum: refers to the minimum concentration of the virus enumerated in a positive sample in the samples in the unit specified.

Maximum: refers to the maximum concentration of the virus enumerated in a positive sample in the samples in the unit specified.

Infectivity results

Total exam: it is the total food samples used in the infectivity essay.

Infectivity (%): Percentage of infectivity in the samples tested.

Quality of molecular method

Inhibition (%): Percentage of inhibition of amplification for the real-time RT-PCR assay. It is assessed with an “external control RNA” - reference RNA that is added in a defined amount to an aliquot of sample RNA and tested using RT-qPCR assay. Comparison of the results of this with the results of EC RNA in the absence of sample RNA enables the determination of the level of RT-PCR inhibition in each sample under test. RT-PCR inhibition levels are used as quality assurance parameters only and are not used to adjust test results. If the RT-PCR inhibition is >75% (undiluted and 10-fold diluted sample RNA), the results are not valid.

Nature of extraction efficiency: Classes are murine norovirus (MNV), Mengovirus, Tulane, MNV and Mengovirus and other.

Extraction efficiency: The extraction efficiency is equal to the process control virus recovery. The “process control virus” is a virus added to the sample portion at the earliest opportunity prior to virus extraction to control for extraction efficiency. If the extraction efficiency is <1%, sample results are not valid and the sample shall be retested. Extraction efficiencies are used as quality assurance parameters only and are not used to adjust test results.

Extraction efficiency range: Minimum-maximum of extraction efficiency in the experiment.

Limit of quantification: Limit of quantification of the method, if provided.

Limit of detection: Limit of detection of the method, if provided.

Replication: Classes are single analysis, duplicate and triplicate.

Warning: To be checked if at least one quantitative result is kept with CT>39 or extra dilution.

2.7.3.3 Outcome data for parasites

The outcome data is for parasites of four types: general results, prevalence results, enumeration results and infectivity results.

General results

Parasite unit: refers to the stages of the parasites and are therefore dependent on the parasite selected. For *Toxoplasma*, the units can be oocysts, tachyzoites, cysts, other and NA; for *Giardia*, cysts, trophozoites, other and NA; and for *Cryptosporidium*, oocysts, sporozoites, other and NA.

Sample weight unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) L, or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit.

EFSA Catalogue and hierarchy: 7.0 UNIT, smpwghUn

PIF Sample weight unit	EFSA terminology	
	Code	Name
g	G148A	g
ml	G156A	ml
L	-	L
unit	-	unit

Basis: stores the basis in which the results are reported, either wet basis or dry basis.

Recovery (0 - ~100%): refers to the recovery rate of parasites with the method employed in this study.

Total units tested (ex. Number of samples): refers to the number of samples submitted for analysis. It corresponds to the metrics of EFSA data models “Total units tested”.

Are results corrected for extraction/recovery? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Are results given after drying? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Bias potential: according to the assessment of methodological quality (Section 2.6), results are marked as potentially biased (1) or not (0).

Reason: If results are marked as potentially biased, the reason must be given.

Comments: Any comments relevant for internal validation assessment.

Prevalence results

Sample weight detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the prevalence essay.

Detected: refers to the number of positive samples.

Enumeration results

Sample weight enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration essay.

Counts unit: It is the unit in which the counts are given: raw numbers per sample weight unit, log base 10 numbers per sample weight unit, or natural logarithm of the numbers per sample weight unit.

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the parasite in the samples in the unit specified.

Mean concentration: median concentration of the parasite in the samples in the unit specified.

Standard deviation: standard deviation of the concentration of the parasite in the samples in the unit specified

Counts vector $\{C_1, \dots, C_9\}$: a vector of the concentration of the parasite in the unit specified, measured in a maximum of nine individual samples.

Minimum: refers to the minimum concentration of the parasite enumerated in a positive sample in the samples in the unit specified.

Maximum: refers to the maximum concentration of the parasite enumerated in a positive sample in the samples in the unit specified.

Infectivity results

Total exam: it is the total samples used in the infectivity essay.

Infectivity (%): Percentage of infectivity in the samples tested.

The eligible articles will be divided by two, so that the two trained reviewers will collect the data independently. At the end, one reviewer will verify the conformity of the data extracted by the other. Any doubts will be solved with the senior reviewer(s) in bimonthly meetings.

3. Maintenance of the Reference Databases

For each SR process, three reference databases will be kept and duly uploaded on the Zenodo Community “Resources of PIF” (<https://zenodo.org/communities/pif>) at the end of every search-insertion period. BibTeX filenames will have the following format (Annex 2):

XYPeriod_WithoutDups.BibTeX: de-duplicated records of studies published in the period X to Y.

XYPeriod_Clean.BibTeX: eligible records of studies ready for insertion in the PIF database, published in the period X to Y.

XYPeriod_CleanFinal.BibTeX: final records whose data were inserted on PIF database, covering studies published in the period X to Y.

4. Modifications to the protocol

Any modification to the present protocol during the implementation of the project will be agreed upon between the parties and will be made effective through written amendment.

5. Funding

This research is funded by EFSA through a grant agreement (GP/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01; 1 September 2022 – 31 August 2026).

6. Disclaimer

EFSA is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information in this protocol.

7. Annexes

Annex 1: Search strategies

Description: Search strategies for retrieving records from four bibliographic databases for systematic reviews linked to the PIF database

Web of Science

TS=(“microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR “microbiological quality” OR “microbiological safety” OR analyses OR analysis OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR detection OR enumeration OR incidence OR investigation OR occurrence OR presence OR prevalence OR sampling OR survey)

AND

TS=(Bacillus cereus OR “B. cereus” OR Clostridium perfringens OR “C. perfringens” OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR ((Escherichia coli OR “E. coli”) AND (pathogenic OR shiga* OR verocytotoxi* OR enterohaemorrhagic OR enterohemorrhagic OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)) OR Listeria monocytogenes OR “L. monocytogenes” OR Staphylococcus aureus OR “S. aureus” OR Yersinia enterocolitica OR “Y. enterocolitica” OR Campylobacter OR “C. jejuni” OR “C. coli” OR Salmonella OR Cryptosporidium OR “C. parvum” OR “C. hominis” OR Giardia OR “G. duodenalis” OR “G. intestinalis” OR “G. cucullus” OR “G. meleagridis” OR “G. ubiquitum” OR “G. canis” OR “G. felis” OR “G. muris” OR “G. viatorum” OR Toxoplasma OR “T. gondii” OR “hepatitis A” OR “hepatitis E” OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR norwalk)

AND

TS=(water OR “soft drink*” OR beverage OR beverages OR coffee OR drink* OR juice* OR smoothie* OR soda* OR tea OR infusion OR meat* OR beef OR bovine OR cow OR veal OR swine OR pork OR piglet OR pig OR ewe OR lamb* OR mutton OR ovine OR sheep OR caprine OR goat* OR horse* OR broiler* OR chicken* OR duck* OR ostrich* OR poultry OR turkey* OR game OR deer OR fowl OR rabbit OR venison OR “wild boar” OR “cold cut*” OR “hot dog*” OR bacon OR bologna OR burger* OR charcuterie OR chorizo* OR deli* OR frankfurter* OR ham* OR hotdog* OR kidney OR liver OR meatball* OR nugget* OR offal OR paté OR pâté OR pate* OR pepperoni* OR salami* OR sausage* OR tongue OR pastrami OR salchichon OR mortadella OR baloney OR boloney OR polony OR terrine* OR rilette* OR steak OR custard OR egg* OR yolk OR albumen OR dairy OR “baby formula” OR “chocolate milk” OR “ice cream” OR “infant formula” OR “infant powder” OR “milk powder” OR butter OR buttermilk OR cheese* OR cream* OR curd* OR dessert* OR fat* OR ice-cream OR milk OR whey OR yoghurt* OR yogurt* OR colostrum OR feta OR brie OR camembert OR “queso blanco” OR chevre OR “blue-vein*” OR “mold ripe*” OR “mould ripe*” OR “Danish blue” OR gorgonzola OR roquefort OR ricotta OR mozzarella OR “dulce de leche” OR “crème fraiche” OR cheddar OR “Parmigiano Reggiano” OR “grana Padano” OR seafood OR seafood* OR “sea food” OR “sea foods” OR “smoked fish” OR “cold smoked” OR “cold-smoked” OR “hot smoked” OR “hot-smoked” OR “dried fish” OR gravad OR graved OR gravlax OR “gravad lax” OR “marinated fish” OR “salted fish” OR anchov* OR clam* OR clams OR cockle* OR cod OR crab* OR crustacean* OR fish* OR halibut OR herring OR lobster* OR mackerel OR mollusc* OR mollusk* OR mussel* OR oyster* OR pollock OR prawn* OR

salmon OR sardine OR scallop* OR shellfish OR shrimp* OR trout OR tuna OR hake OR crayfish OR bivalve* OR carp OR caviar OR squid OR cuttlefish OR cockle OR cockles OR snail OR eel OR sturgeon OR vegetable* OR produce OR “germinated seed*” OR “green salad*” OR “leafy green” OR “leafy greens” OR “mixed salad*” OR “mixed vegetable*” OR “pre-cut salad*” OR “vegetable mix” OR fungi OR herb* OR lettuce OR mushroom* OR salad* OR spinach OR sprout* OR veggie* OR “raw produc*” OR “frozen produc*” OR microgreens OR avocado* OR salad* OR tomato* OR guacamole* OR taboulé OR pea OR peas OR bean OR beans OR chickpea* OR sprout* OR carrot OR carrots OR broccoli* OR beetroot* OR corn OR lentil* OR cucumber* OR legume* OR “dried seed*” OR “dry seed*” OR nut* OR oilseed* OR spice* OR pepper OR cinnamon OR turmeric OR cumin OR oregano OR nutmeg OR rosemary OR saffron OR basil OR garlic OR pulses OR almond OR sesame OR grain* OR bakery OR bread* OR cake* OR cereal* OR confectionary OR flakes OR flour OR maize OR pastries OR pastry OR rice OR seed* OR wheat OR fruit* OR “fruit mix” OR “fruit salad” OR “mixed fruit” OR “sliced fruit” OR “stone fruit” OR berries OR berry OR citrus* OR drupe* OR pome* OR apple* OR banana* OR melon* OR peach* OR fat OR oil* OR sugar* OR syrup* OR honey OR chocolate OR meal OR meals OR food OR foods OR “buffet meal*” OR “complex food” OR “frozen meal*” OR multi-ingredient OR “multi ingredient” OR “probiotic drink*” OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR “ready meal” OR “ready prepared” OR “ready to eat” OR “sous vide” OR coleslaw OR composite* OR convenience OR cured OR dip OR dips OR dish OR dishes OR dressing* OR dumpling* OR fermented OR filling OR gravy OR hummus OR jam* OR kebab OR macerated OR marinad* OR marinate* OR mayonnaise OR pasta OR pizza OR pickled OR preserved OR pudding* OR puree* OR salsa OR salsas OR salted OR sandwich* OR sashimi OR ceviche OR sauce* OR smoked OR snack OR snacks OR soup OR soups OR stew* OR surimi OR sushi OR tofu* OR topping* OR vegan OR vegetarian OR chowder OR tahini)

AND

(AD=(Albania OR Andorra OR Armenia OR Austria OR Azerbaijan OR Belarus OR Belgium OR Bosnia and Herzegovina OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark OR England OR Estonia OR Finland OR France OR Georgia OR Germany OR Greece OR Hungary OR Iceland OR Ireland OR Italy OR Kazakhstan OR Kosovo OR Latvia OR Liechtenstein OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Macedonia OR Malta OR Moldova OR Monaco OR Montenegro OR Netherlands OR North Macedonia OR Norway OR Poland OR Portugal OR Romania OR Russia OR San Marino OR Serbia OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Scotland OR Spain OR Sweden OR Switzerland OR Turkey OR Ukraine OR United Kingdom OR UK OR Vatican OR Wales OR Yugoslavia OR Europe* OR EU)

OR

TS=(Albania OR Andorra OR Armenia OR Austria OR Azerbaijan OR Belarus OR Belgium OR Bosnia and Herzegovina OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark OR England OR Estonia OR Finland OR France OR Georgia OR Germany OR Greece OR Hungary OR Iceland OR Ireland OR Italy OR Kazakhstan OR Kosovo OR Latvia OR Liechtenstein OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Macedonia OR Malta OR Moldova OR Monaco OR Montenegro OR Netherlands OR North Macedonia OR Norway OR Poland OR Portugal OR Romania OR Russia OR San Marino OR Serbia OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Scotland OR Spain OR Sweden OR Switzerland OR Turkey OR Ukraine OR United Kingdom OR UK OR Vatican OR Wales OR Yugoslavia OR Europe* OR EU))

NOT

TS=(“in vitro” OR “in-vitro” OR “challenge study” OR “essential oil*” OR antimicrobial* OR attribution OR biofilm* OR “plant extract” OR “extracts” OR feed OR livestock OR sanitiser OR sanitizer OR spiked OR “feed supplement*”)

Filter mechanisms to be applied:

i. Collections to be searched

Advanced Search > Search In: > Web of Science Core Collection > Edition: > ‘Science Citation Index Expanded’ and ‘Emerging Sources Citation Index’

ii. Country of origin of the study

Selection of European countries only already provided in the query string

iii. Date of database insertion

Advanced Search > Add date range: > Index Date > Custom (YYYY-MM-DD to YYYY-MM-DD)

[or in the query string, add: AND LD=(YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD)]

iv. Year of publication

Filter by desired year of publication

[or in the query string, add: AND (PY=="YYYY")]

v. Type of publication (primary research articles and reviews)

Filter by document types ‘Article’ and ‘Review article’

[or in the query string, add: AND DT=("ARTICLE" OR "REVIEW")]

vi. Language (English, Spanish, French, Portuguese)

Filter by languages ‘English’, ‘Spanish’, ‘French’ and ‘Portuguese’

[or in the query string, add: AND LA=("ENGLISH" OR "SPANISH" OR "FRENCH" OR "PORTUGUESE")]

PubMed

("microbial quality"[tiab] OR "microbial safety"[tiab] OR "microbiological quality"[tiab] OR "microbiological safety"[tiab] OR analyses[tiab] OR analysis[tiab] OR concentration[tiab] OR contamination[tiab] OR count*[tiab] OR detection[tiab] OR enumeration[tiab] OR incidence[tiab] OR investigation[tiab] OR occurrence[tiab] OR presence[tiab] OR prevalence[tiab] OR sampling[tiab] OR survey[tiab])

AND

(Bacillus cereus[tiab] OR "B. cereus"[tiab] OR Clostridium perfringens[tiab] OR "C. perfringens"[tiab] OR STEC[tiab] OR VTEC[tiab] OR EHEC[tiab] OR ((Escherichia coli[tiab] OR "E. coli"[tiab]) AND (pathogenic[tiab] OR shiga*[tiab] OR verocytotoxi*[tiab] OR enterohaemorrhagic[tiab] OR enterohemorrhagic[tiab] OR O157[tiab] OR O157:H7[tiab] OR O26:H11[tiab] OR O145:H28[tiab] OR O103:H2[tiab] OR O111:H8[tiab] OR O104:H4[tiab])) OR Listeria monocytogenes[tiab] OR "L. monocytogenes"[tiab] OR Staphylococcus aureus[tiab] OR "S. aureus"[tiab] OR Yersinia enterocolitica[tiab] OR "Y. enterocolitica"[tiab] OR Campylobacter[tiab] OR "C. jejuni"[tiab] OR "C. coli"[tiab] OR Salmonella[tiab] OR Cryptosporidium[tiab] OR "C. parvum"[tiab] OR "C. hominis"[tiab] OR Giardia[tiab] OR "G. duodenalis"[tiab] OR "G. intestinalis"[tiab] OR "G. cucullus"[tiab] OR "G. meleagridis"[tiab] OR "G. ubiquitum"[tiab] OR "G. canis"[tiab] OR "G. felis"[tiab] OR "G. muris"[tiab] OR "G. viatorum"[tiab] OR Toxoplasma[tiab] OR "T. gondii"[tiab] OR "hepatitis A"[tiab] OR "hepatitis E"[tiab] OR HAV[tiab] OR HEV[tiab] OR norovirus[tiab] OR norwalk[tiab])

AND

(water[tiab] OR “soft drink*”[tiab] OR beverage[tiab] OR beverages[tiab] OR coffee[tiab] OR drink*[tiab] OR juice*[tiab] OR smoothie*[tiab] OR soda*[tiab] OR tea[tiab] OR infusion[tiab] OR meat*[tiab] OR beef[tiab] OR bovine[tiab] OR cow[tiab] OR veal[tiab] OR swine[tiab] OR pork[tiab] OR piglet[tiab] OR pig[tiab] OR ewe[tiab] OR lamb*[tiab] OR mutton[tiab] OR ovine[tiab] OR sheep[tiab] OR caprine[tiab] OR goat*[tiab] OR horse*[tiab] OR broiler*[tiab] OR chicken*[tiab] OR duck*[tiab] OR ostrich*[tiab] OR poultry[tiab] OR turkey*[tiab] OR game[tiab] OR deer[tiab] OR fowl[tiab] OR rabbit[tiab] OR venison[tiab] OR “wild boar”[tiab] OR “cold cut*”[tiab] OR “hot dog*”[tiab] OR bacon[tiab] OR bologna[tiab] OR burger*[tiab] OR charcuterie[tiab] OR chorizo*[tiab] OR deli*[tiab] OR frankfurter*[tiab] OR ham*[tiab] OR hotdog*[tiab] OR kidney[tiab] OR liver[tiab] OR meatball*[tiab] OR nugget*[tiab] OR offal[tiab] OR paté[tiab] OR pâté[tiab] OR pate*[tiab] OR pepperoni*[tiab] OR salami*[tiab] OR sausage*[tiab] OR tongue[tiab] OR pastrami[tiab] OR salchichon[tiab] OR mortadella[tiab] OR baloney[tiab] OR boloney[tiab] OR polony[tiab] OR terrine*[tiab] OR rilette*[tiab] OR steak[tiab] OR custard[tiab] OR egg*[tiab] OR yolk[tiab] OR albumen[tiab] OR dairy[tiab] OR “baby formula”[tiab] OR “chocolate milk”[tiab] OR “ice cream”[tiab] OR “infant formula”[tiab] OR “infant powder”[tiab] OR “milk powder”[tiab] OR butter[tiab] OR buttermilk[tiab] OR cheese*[tiab] OR cream*[tiab] OR curd*[tiab] OR dessert*[tiab] OR fat*[tiab] OR ice-cream[tiab] OR milk[tiab] OR whey[tiab] OR yoghurt*[tiab] OR yogurt*[tiab] OR colostrum[tiab] OR feta[tiab] OR brie[tiab] OR camembert[tiab] OR “queso blanco”[tiab] OR chevre[tiab] OR “blue-vein*”[tiab] OR “mold ripe*”[tiab] OR “mould ripe*”[tiab] OR “Danish blue”[tiab] OR gorgonzola[tiab] OR roquefort[tiab] OR ricotta[tiab] OR mozzarella[tiab] OR “dulce de leche”[tiab] OR “crème fraiche”[tiab] OR cheddar[tiab] OR “Parmigiano Reggiano”[tiab] OR “grana Padano”[tiab] OR seafood[tiab] OR seafood*[tiab] OR “sea food”[tiab] OR “sea foods”[tiab] OR “smoked fish”[tiab] OR “cold smoked”[tiab] OR “cold-smoked”[tiab] OR “hot smoked”[tiab] OR “hot-smoked”[tiab] OR “dried fish”[tiab] OR gravad[tiab] OR graved[tiab] OR gravlax[tiab] OR “gravad lax”[tiab] OR “marinated fish”[tiab] OR “salted fish”[tiab] OR anchov*[tiab] OR clam*[tiab] OR clams[tiab] OR cockle*[tiab] OR cod[tiab] OR crab*[tiab] OR crustacean*[tiab] OR fish*[tiab] OR halibut[tiab] OR herring[tiab] OR lobster*[tiab] OR mackerel[tiab] OR mollusc*[tiab] OR mollusk*[tiab] OR mussel*[tiab] OR oyster*[tiab] OR pollock[tiab] OR prawn*[tiab] OR salmon[tiab] OR sardine[tiab] OR scallop*[tiab] OR shellfish[tiab] OR shrimp*[tiab] OR trout[tiab] OR tuna[tiab] OR hake[tiab] OR crayfish [tiab] OR bivalve*[tiab] OR carp[tiab] OR caviar[tiab] OR squid[tiab] OR cuttlefish[tiab] OR cockle[tiab] OR cockles[tiab] OR snail[tiab] OR eel[tiab] OR sturgeon[tiab] OR vegetable*[tiab] OR produce[tiab] OR “germinated seed*”[tiab] OR “green salad*”[tiab] OR “leafy green”[tiab] OR “leafy greens”[tiab] OR “mixed salad*”[tiab] OR “mixed vegetable*”[tiab] OR “pre-cut salad*”[tiab] OR “vegetable mix”[tiab] OR fungi[tiab] OR herb*[tiab] OR lettuce[tiab] OR mushroom*[tiab] OR salad*[tiab] OR spinach[tiab] OR sprout*[tiab] OR veggie*[tiab] OR “raw produc*”[tiab] OR “frozen produc*”[tiab] OR microgreens[tiab] OR avocado*[tiab] OR salad*[tiab] OR tomato*[tiab] OR guacamole*[tiab] OR taboulé[tiab] OR pea[tiab] OR peas[tiab] OR bean[tiab] OR beans[tiab] OR chickpea*[tiab] OR sprout*[tiab] OR carrot[tiab] OR carrots[tiab] OR broccoli*[tiab] OR beetroot*[tiab] OR corn[tiab] OR lentil*[tiab] OR cucumber*[tiab] OR legume*[tiab] OR “dried seed*”[tiab] OR “dry seed*”[tiab] OR nut*[tiab] OR oilseed*[tiab] OR spice*[tiab] OR pepper[tiab] OR cinnamon[tiab] OR turmeric[tiab] OR cumin[tiab] OR oregano[tiab] OR nutmeg[tiab] OR rosemary[tiab] OR saffron[tiab] OR basil[tiab] OR garlic[tiab] OR pulses[tiab] OR almond[tiab] OR sesame[tiab] OR grain*[tiab] OR bakery[tiab] OR bread*[tiab] OR cake*[tiab] OR cereal*[tiab] OR confectionary[tiab] OR flakes[tiab] OR flour[tiab] OR maize[tiab] OR pastries[tiab] OR pastry[tiab] OR rice[tiab] OR seed*[tiab] OR wheat[tiab] OR fruit*[tiab] OR “fruit mix”[tiab] OR “fruit salad”[tiab] OR “mixed fruit”[tiab] OR “sliced fruit”[tiab] OR “stone fruit”[tiab] OR berries[tiab] OR berry[tiab] OR citrus*[tiab] OR drupe*[tiab] OR pome*[tiab] OR apple*[tiab] OR banana*[tiab] OR melon*[tiab] OR peach*[tiab] OR fat[tiab] OR oil*[tiab] OR sugar*[tiab] OR syrup*[tiab] OR honey[tiab] OR chocolate[tiab] OR meal[tiab] OR

meals[tiab] OR food[tiab] OR foods[tiab] OR “buffet meal*”[tiab] OR “complex food”[tiab] OR “frozen meal*”[tiab] OR multi-ingredient[tiab] OR “multi ingredient”[tiab] OR “probiotic drink*”[tiab] OR ready-to-eat[tiab] OR RTE[tiab] OR “ready meal”[tiab] OR “ready prepared”[tiab] OR “ready to eat”[tiab] OR “sous vide”[tiab] OR coleslaw[tiab] OR composite*[tiab] OR convenience[tiab] OR cured[tiab] OR dip[tiab] OR dips[tiab] OR dish[tiab] OR dishes[tiab] OR dressing*[tiab] OR dumpling*[tiab] OR fermented[tiab] OR filling[tiab] OR gravy[tiab] OR hummus[tiab] OR jam*[tiab] OR kebab[tiab] OR macerated[tiab] OR marinad*[tiab] OR marinate*[tiab] OR mayonnaise[tiab] OR pasta[tiab] OR pizza[tiab] OR pickled[tiab] OR preserved[tiab] OR pudding*[tiab] OR puree*[tiab] OR salsa[tiab] OR salsas[tiab] OR salted[tiab] OR sandwich*[tiab] OR sashimi[tiab] OR ceviche[tiab] OR sauce*[tiab] OR smoked[tiab] OR snack[tiab] OR snacks[tiab] OR soup[tiab] OR soups[tiab] OR stew*[tiab] OR surimi[tiab] OR sushi[tiab] OR tofu*[tiab] OR topping*[tiab] OR vegan[tiab] OR vegetarian[tiab] OR chowder[tiab] OR tahini[tiab])

AND

((Albania[ad] OR Andorra[ad] OR Armenia[ad] OR Austria[ad] OR Azerbaijan[ad] OR Belarus[ad] OR Belgium[ad] OR Bosnia and Herzegovina[ad] OR Bulgaria[ad] OR Croatia[ad] OR Cyprus[ad] OR Czech Republic[ad] OR Denmark[ad] OR England[ad] OR Estonia[ad] OR Finland[ad] OR France[ad] OR Georgia[ad] OR Germany[ad] OR Greece[ad] OR Hungary[ad] OR Iceland[ad] OR Ireland[ad] OR Italy[ad] OR Kazakhstan[ad] OR Kosovo[ad] OR Latvia[ad] OR Liechtenstein[ad] OR Lithuania[ad] OR Luxembourg[ad] OR Macedonia[ad] OR Malta[ad] OR Moldova[ad] OR Monaco[ad] OR Montenegro[ad] OR Netherlands[ad] OR North Macedonia[ad] OR Norway[ad] OR Poland[ad] OR Portugal[ad] OR Romania[ad] OR Russia[ad] OR San Marino[ad] OR Serbia[ad] OR Slovakia[ad] OR Slovenia[ad] OR Scotland[ad] OR Spain[ad] OR Sweden[ad] OR Switzerland[ad] OR Turkey[ad] OR Ukraine[ad] OR United Kingdom[ad] OR UK[ad] OR Vatican[ad] OR Wales[ad] OR Yugoslavia[ad] OR Europe*[ad] OR EU[ad])

OR

(Albania[tiab] OR Andorra[tiab] OR Armenia[tiab] OR Austria[tiab] OR Azerbaijan[tiab] OR Belarus[tiab] OR Belgium[tiab] OR Bosnia and Herzegovina[tiab] OR Bulgaria[tiab] OR Croatia[tiab] OR Cyprus[tiab] OR Czech Republic[tiab] OR Denmark[tiab] OR England[tiab] OR Estonia[tiab] OR Finland[tiab] OR France[tiab] OR Georgia[tiab] OR Germany[tiab] OR Greece[tiab] OR Hungary[tiab] OR Iceland[tiab] OR Ireland[tiab] OR Italy[tiab] OR Kazakhstan[tiab] OR Kosovo[tiab] OR Latvia[tiab] OR Liechtenstein[tiab] OR Lithuania[tiab] OR Luxembourg[tiab] OR Macedonia[tiab] OR Malta[tiab] OR Moldova[tiab] OR Monaco[tiab] OR Montenegro[tiab] OR Netherlands[tiab] OR North Macedonia[tiab] OR Norway[tiab] OR Poland[tiab] OR Portugal[tiab] OR Romania[tiab] OR Russia[tiab] OR San Marino[tiab] OR Serbia[tiab] OR Slovakia[tiab] OR Slovenia[tiab] OR Scotland[tiab] OR Spain[tiab] OR Sweden[tiab] OR Switzerland[tiab] OR Turkey[tiab] OR Ukraine[tiab] OR United Kingdom[tiab] OR UK[tiab] OR Vatican[tiab] OR Wales[tiab] OR Yugoslavia[tiab] OR Europe*[tiab] OR EU[tiab])

OR

(Albania[mh] OR Andorra[mh] OR Armenia[mh] OR Austria[mh] OR Azerbaijan[mh] OR Belarus[mh] OR Belgium[mh] OR Bosnia and Herzegovina[mh] OR Bulgaria[mh] OR Croatia[mh] OR Cyprus[mh] OR Czech Republic[mh] OR Denmark[mh] OR England[mh] OR Estonia[mh] OR Finland[mh] OR France[mh] OR Georgia[mh] OR Germany[mh] OR Greece[mh] OR Hungary[mh] OR Iceland[mh] OR Ireland[mh] OR Italy[mh] OR Kazakhstan[mh] OR Kosovo[mh] OR Latvia[mh] OR Liechtenstein[mh] OR Lithuania[mh] OR Luxembourg[mh] OR Macedonia[mh] OR Malta[mh] OR Moldova[mh] OR Monaco[mh] OR Montenegro[mh] OR Netherlands[mh] OR North Macedonia[mh] OR Norway[mh] OR Poland[mh] OR Portugal[mh] OR Romania[mh] OR Russia[mh] OR San Marino[mh] OR Serbia[mh] OR Slovakia[mh] OR Slovenia[mh] OR Scotland[mh] OR Spain[mh] OR Sweden[mh] OR Switzerland[mh] OR Turkey[mh] OR Ukraine[mh] OR United Kingdom[mh])

OR UK[mh] OR Vatican[mh] OR Wales[mh] OR Yugoslavia[mh] OR Europe*[mh] OR EU[mh]))

NOT

("in vitro"[tiab] OR "in-vitro"[tiab] OR "challenge study"[tiab] OR "essential oil*" [tiab] OR antimicrobial*[tiab] OR attribution[tiab] OR biofilm*[tiab] OR "plant extract"[tiab] OR "extracts"[tiab] OR feed[tiab] OR livestock[tiab] OR sanitiser[tiab] OR sanitizer[tiab] OR spiked[tiab] OR "feed supplement*" [tiab])

NOT

(bookdocs[filter] OR congress[filter] OR englishabstract[filter])

Filter mechanisms to be applied:

i. Country of origin of the study

Selection of European countries only already provided in the query string

ii. Date of database insertion

Advanced Search > Add terms to the query box> Date- Entry > AND (YYYY-MM-DD to YYYY-MM-DD)

[or in the query string, add: AND (YYYY/MM/DD:YYYY/MM/DD[edat])]

iii. Year of publication

Filter by desired custom period of publication (YYYY-MM-DD to YYYY-MM-DD)

[or in the query string, add: AND (YYYY/MM/DD:YYYY/MM/DD[pdat])]

iv. Type of publication (primary research articles and reviews)

Exclusion of 'Books', 'Congress' and 'English Abstracts' already provided in the query string

v. Language (English, Spanish, French, Portuguese, undetermined)

Filter by languages 'English', 'Spanish', 'French', 'Portuguese' and 'undetermined'

[or in the query string, add: AND (english[la] OR spanish[la] OR french[la] OR portuguese[la] OR undetermined[la])]

Scopus

(TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbial quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbial safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbiological quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbiological safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(concentration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(contamination) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(count*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(detection) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(enumeration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(incidence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(investigation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(occurrence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(presence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(prevalence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sampling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(survey))

AND

(TITLE-ABS-KEY(Bacillus cereus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("B. cereus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Clostridium perfringens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("C. perfringens") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(STEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(VTEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(EHEC) OR ((TITLE-ABS-KEY(Escherichia coli) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("E. coli"))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY(pathogenic) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(shiga*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(verocytotoxi*) OR TITLE-ABS-

KEY(enterohaemorrhagic) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(enterohemorrhagic) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O157) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O157:H7) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O26:H11) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O145:H28) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O103:H2) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O111:H8) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(O104:H4))) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Listeria monocytogenes*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("L. monocytogenes") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Staphylococcus aureus*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("S. aureus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Yersinia enterocolitica*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("Y. enterocolitica") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Campylobacter*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("C. jejuni") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("C. coli") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Salmonella*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Cryptosporidium*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("C. parvum") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("C. hominis") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Giardia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. duodenalis") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. intestinalis") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. cuniculus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. meleagridis") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. ubiquitum") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. canis") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. felis") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. muris") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("G. viatorum") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(*Toxoplasma*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("T. gondii") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("hepatitis A") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("hepatitis E") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(HAV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(HEV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(norovirus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(norwalk))

AND

(TITLE-ABS-KEY(water) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("soft drink*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(beverage) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(beverages) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(coffee) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(drink*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(juice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(smoothie*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(soda*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tea) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(infusion) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(beef) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bovine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cow) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(veal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(swine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pork) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(piglet) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pig) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ewe) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lamb*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mutton) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ovine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sheep) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(caprine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(goat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(horse*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(broiler*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chicken*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(duck*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ostrich*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(poultry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(turkey*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(game) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(deer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fowl) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rabbit) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(venison) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("wild boar") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("cold cut*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("hot dog*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bacon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bologna) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(burger*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(charcuterie) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chorizo*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(deli*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(frankfurter*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ham*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hotdog*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(kidney) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(liver) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meatball*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(nugget*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(offal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(paté) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pâté) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pate*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pepperoni*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salami*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sausage*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tongue) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pastrami) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salchichon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mortadella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(baloney) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(boloney) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(polony) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(terrines*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rillettes*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(steak) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(custard) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(egg*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(yolk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(albumen) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dairy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("baby formula") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("chocolate milk") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("ice cream") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("infant formula") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("infant powder") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("milk powder") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(butter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(buttermilk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cheese*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cream*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(curd*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dessert*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ice-cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(milk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(whey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(yoghurt*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(yogurt*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(colostrum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(feta) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY(brie) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(camembert) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“queso blanco”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chevre) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“blue-vein”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mold ripe”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mould ripe”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“Danish blue”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gorgonzola) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(roquefort) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ricotta) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mozzarella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“dulce de leche”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“crème fraiche”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cheddar) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“Parmigiano Reggiano”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“grana Padano”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seafood) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seafood*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea food”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea foods”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“smoked fish”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“cold smoked”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“cold-smoked”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“hot smoked”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“hot-smoked”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“dried fish”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravad) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravaded) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravlax) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“gravad lax”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“marinated fish”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“salted fish”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(anchov*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(clam*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(clams) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cockle*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cod) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crab*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crustacean*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fish*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(halibut) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(herring) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lobster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mackerel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mollusc*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mollusk*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mussel*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(oyster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pollock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(prawn*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salmon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sardine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scallop*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(shellfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(shrimp*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(trout) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tuna) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hake) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crayfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bivalve*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(carp) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(caviar) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(squid) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cuttlefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cockle) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cockles) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snail) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(eel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sturgeon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(vegetable*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(produce) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“germinated seed”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“green salad”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“leafy green”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“leafy greens”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mixed salad”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mixed vegetable”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“pre-cut salad”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“vegetable mix”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fungi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(herb*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lettuce) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mushroom*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salad*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(spinach) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sprout*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(veggie*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“raw produc”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“frozen produc”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(microgreens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(avocado*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salad*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tomato*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(guacamole*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(taboulé) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pea) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(peas) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bean) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(beans) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chickpea*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sprout*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(carrot) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(carrots) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(broccoli*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(beetroot*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(corn) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lentil*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cucumber*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(legume*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“dried seed”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“dry seed”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(nut*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(oilseed*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(spice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pepper) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cinnamon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(turmeric) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cumin) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(oregano) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(nutmeg) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rosemary) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(saffron) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(basil) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(garlic) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pulses) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(almond) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sesame) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(grain*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bakery) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bread*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cake*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cereal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(confectionary) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(flakes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(flour) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(maize) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pastries) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pastry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rice) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seed*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(wheat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fruit*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“fruit mix”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“fruit salad”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mixed fruit”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sliced

fruit”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“stone fruit”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(berries) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(berry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(citrus*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(drupe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pome*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(apple*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(banana*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(melon*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(peach*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(oil*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sugar*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(syrup*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(honey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chocolate) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meals) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(food) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(foods) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“buffet meal”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“complex food”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“frozen meal”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(multi-ingredient) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“multi ingredient”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“probiotic drink”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ready-to-eat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(RTE) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“ready meal”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“ready prepared”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“ready to eat”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sous vide”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(coleslaw) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(composite*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(convenience) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cured) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dip) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dips) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dishes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dressing*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dumpling*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fermented) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(filling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hummus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(jam*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(kebab) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(macerated) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(marinad*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(marinate*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mayonnaise) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pasta) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pizza) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pickled) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(preserved) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pudding*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(puree*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salsa) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salsas) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salted) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sandwich*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sashimi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ceviche) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sauce*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(smoked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snack) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snacks) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(soup) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(soups) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(stew*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(surimi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sushi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tofu*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(topping*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(vegan) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(vegetarian) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chowder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tahini))

AND

((AFFIL(Albania) OR AFFIL(Andorra) OR AFFIL(Armenia) OR AFFIL(Austria) OR AFFIL(Azerbaijan) OR AFFIL(Belarus) OR AFFIL(Belgium) OR AFFIL(Bosnia and Herzegovina) OR AFFIL(Bulgaria) OR AFFIL(Croatia) OR AFFIL(Cyprus) OR AFFIL(Czech Republic) OR AFFIL(Denmark) OR AFFIL(England) OR AFFIL(Estonia) OR AFFIL(Finland) OR AFFIL(France) OR AFFIL(Georgia) OR AFFIL(Germany) OR AFFIL(Greece) OR AFFIL(Hungary) OR AFFIL(Iceland) OR AFFIL(Ireland) OR AFFIL(Italy) OR AFFIL(Kazakhstan) OR AFFIL(Kosovo) OR AFFIL(Latvia) OR AFFIL(Liechtenstein) OR AFFIL(Lithuania) OR AFFIL(Luxembourg) OR AFFIL(Macedonia) OR AFFIL(Malta) OR AFFIL(Moldova) OR AFFIL(Monaco) OR AFFIL(Montenegro) OR AFFIL(Netherlands) OR AFFIL(North Macedonia) OR AFFIL(Norway) OR AFFIL(Poland) OR AFFIL(Portugal) OR AFFIL(Romania) OR AFFIL(Russia) OR AFFIL(San Marino) OR AFFIL(Serbia) OR AFFIL(Slovakia) OR AFFIL(Slovenia) OR AFFIL(Scotland) OR AFFIL(Spain) OR AFFIL(Sweden) OR AFFIL(Switzerland) OR AFFIL(Turkey) OR AFFIL(Ukraine) OR AFFIL(United Kingdom) OR AFFIL(UK) OR AFFIL(Vatican) OR AFFIL(Wales) OR AFFIL(Yugoslavia) OR AFFIL(Europe*) OR AFFIL(EU))

OR

(TITLE-ABS-KEY(Albania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Andorra) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Armenia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Austria) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Azerbaijan) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Belarus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Belgium) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Bosnia and Herzegovina) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Bulgaria) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Croatia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Cyprus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Czech Republic) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Denmark) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(England) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Estonia) OR TITLE-ABS-

KEY(Finland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(France) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Georgia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Germany) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Greece) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Hungary) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Iceland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Ireland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Italy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Kazakhstan) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Kosovo) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Latvia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Liechtenstein) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Lithuania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Luxembourg) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Macedonia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Malta) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Moldova) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Monaco) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Montenegro) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Netherlands) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(North Macedonia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Norway) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Poland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Portugal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Romania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Russia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(San Marino) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Serbia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Slovakia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Slovenia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Scotland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Spain) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Sweden) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Switzerland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Turkey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Ukraine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(United Kingdom) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(UK) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Vatican) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Wales) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Yugoslavia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(EU))

AND NOT

(TITLE-ABS-KEY("in vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("in-vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("challenge study") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("essential oil*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(antimicrobial*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(attribution) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(biofilm*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("plant extract") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("extracts") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(feed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(livestock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sanitiser) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sanitizer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(spiked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("feed supplement*"))

Filter mechanisms to be applied:

i. Country of origin of the study

Selection of European countries only already provided in the query string

ii. Date of database insertion

In the query string, add: AND ((LOAD-DATE AFT YYYYMMDD) AND (LOAD-DATE BEF YYYYMMDD))

iii. Year of publication

Filter by desired year of publication

[or in the query string, add: AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2022))]

iv. Type of publication (primary research articles, reviews, undefined)

Filter by document types 'Article', 'Review' and "Undefined"

[or in the query string, add: AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"Undefined"))]

v. Language (English, Spanish, French, Portuguese, undefined)

Filter by languages 'English', 'Spanish', 'French', 'Portuguese' and "Undefined"

[or in the query string, add: AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"French") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Spanish") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Portuguese") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Undefined"))]

Records from SciELO will be recovered joining the results from three strings:

String #1

((“microbial quality”) OR (“microbial safety”) OR (“microbiological quality”) OR (“microbiological safety”) OR (analyses) OR (analysis) OR (concentration) OR (contamination) OR (count*) OR (detection) OR (enumeration) OR (incidence) OR (investigation) OR (occurrence) OR (presence) OR (prevalence) OR (sampling) OR (survey))

AND

((Bacillus cereus) OR (“B. cereus”) OR (Clostridium perfringens) OR (“C. perfringens”) OR (STEC) OR (VTEC) OR (EHEC) OR (((Escherichia coli) OR (“E. coli”)) AND ((pathogenic) OR (shiga*) OR (verocytotoxi*) OR (enterohaemorrhagic) OR (enterohemorrhagic) OR (O157) OR (O157:H7) OR (O26:H11) OR (O145:H28) OR (O103:H2) OR (O111:H8) OR (O104:H4))) OR (Listeria monocytogenes) OR (“L. monocytogenes”) OR (Staphylococcus aureus) OR (“S. aureus”) OR (Yersinia enterocolitica) OR (“Y. enterocolitica”) OR (Campylobacter) OR (“C. jejuni”) OR (“C. coli”) OR (Salmonella) OR (Cryptosporidium) OR (“C. parvum”) OR (“C. hominis”) OR (Giardia) OR (“G. duodenalis”) OR (“G. intestinalis”) OR (“G. cuniculus”) OR (“G. meleagridis”) OR (“G. ubiquitum”) OR (“G. canis”) OR (“G. felis”) OR (“G. muris”) OR (“G. viatorum”) OR (Toxoplasma) OR (“T. gondii”) OR (“hepatitis A”) OR (“hepatitis E”) OR (HAV) OR (HEV) OR (norovirus) OR (norwalk))

AND

((water) OR (“soft drink*”) OR (beverage) OR (beverages) OR (coffee) OR (drink*) OR (juice*) OR (smoothie*) OR (soda*) OR (tea) OR (infusion) OR (meat*) OR (beef) OR (bovine) OR (cow) OR (veal) OR (swine) OR (pork) OR (piglet) OR (pig) OR (ewe) OR (lamb*) OR (mutton) OR (ovine) OR (sheep) OR (caprine) OR (goat*) OR (horse*) OR (broiler*) OR (chicken*) OR (duck*) OR (ostrich*) OR (poultry) OR (turkey*) OR (game) OR (deer) OR (fowl) OR (rabbit) OR (venison) OR (“wild boar”) OR (“cold cut*”) OR (“hot dog*”) OR (bacon) OR (bologna) OR (burger*) OR (charcuterie) OR (chorizo*) OR (deli*) OR (frankfurter*) OR (ham*) OR (hotdog*) OR (kidney) OR (liver) OR (meatball*) OR (nugget*) OR (offal) OR (paté) OR (pâté) OR (pate*) OR (pepperoni*) OR (salami*) OR (sausage*) OR (tongue) OR (pastrami) OR (salchichon) OR (mortadella) OR (baloney) OR (boloney) OR (polony) OR (terrines*) OR (rilette*) OR (steak) OR (custard) OR (egg*) OR (yolk) OR (albumen) OR (dairy) OR (“baby formula”) OR (“chocolate milk”) OR (“ice cream”) OR (“infant formula”) OR (“infant powder”) OR (“milk powder”) OR (butter) OR (buttermilk) OR (cheese*) OR (cream*) OR (curd*) OR (dessert*) OR (fat*) OR (ice-cream) OR (milk) OR (whey) OR (yoghurt*) OR (yogurt*) OR (colostrum) OR (feta) OR (brie) OR (camembert) OR (“queso blanco”) OR (chevre) OR (“blue-vein*”) OR (“mold ripe*”) OR (“mould ripe*”) OR (“Danish blue”) OR (gorgonzola) OR (roquefort) OR (ricotta) OR (mozzarella) OR (“dulce de leche”) OR (“crème fraiche”) OR (cheddar) OR (“Parmigiano Reggiano”) OR (“grana Padano”))

AND NOT

((“in vitro”) OR (“in-vitro”) OR (“challenge study”) OR (“essential oil*”) OR (antimicrobial*) OR (attribution) OR (biofilm*) OR (“plant extract”) OR (“extracts”) OR (feed) OR (livestock) OR (sanitiser) OR (sanitizer) OR (spiked) OR (“feed supplement*”))

String #2

((“microbial quality”) OR (“microbial safety”) OR (“microbiological quality”) OR (“microbiological safety”) OR (analyses) OR (analysis) OR (concentration) OR (contamination) OR (count*) OR (detection) OR (enumeration) OR (incidence) OR (investigation) OR (occurrence) OR (presence) OR (prevalence) OR (sampling) OR (survey))

AND

((Bacillus cereus) OR (“B. cereus”) OR (Clostridium perfringens) OR (“C. perfringens”) OR (STEC) OR (VTEC) OR (EHEC) OR ((Escherichia coli) OR (“E. coli”)) AND ((pathogenic) OR (shiga*) OR (verocytotoxi*) OR (enterohaemorrhagic) OR (enterohemorrhagic) OR (O157) OR (O157:H7) OR (O26:H11) OR (O145:H28) OR (O103:H2) OR (O111:H8) OR (O104:H4))) OR (Listeria monocytogenes) OR (“L. monocytogenes”) OR (Staphylococcus aureus) OR (“S. aureus”) OR (Yersinia enterocolitica) OR (“Y. enterocolitica”) OR (Campylobacter) OR (“C. jejuni”) OR (“C. coli”) OR (Salmonella) OR (Cryptosporidium) OR (“C. parvum”) OR (“C. hominis”) OR (Giardia) OR (“G. duodenalis”) OR (“G. intestinalis”) OR (“G. cuniculus”) OR (“G. meleagridis”) OR (“G. ubiquitum”) OR (“G. canis”) OR (“G. felis”) OR (“G. muris”) OR (“G. viatorum”) OR (Toxoplasma) OR (“T. gondii”) OR (“hepatitis A”) OR (“hepatitis E”) OR (HAV) OR (HEV) OR (norovirus) OR (norwalk))

AND

((seafood) OR (seafood*) OR (“sea food”) OR (“sea foods”) OR (“smoked fish”) OR (“cold smoked”) OR (“cold-smoked”) OR (“hot smoked”) OR (“hot-smoked”) OR (“dried fish”) OR (gravad) OR (graved) OR (gravlax) OR (“gravad lax”) OR (“marinated fish”) OR (“salted fish”) OR (anchov*) OR (clam*) OR (clams) OR (cockle*) OR (cod) OR (crab*) OR (crustacean*) OR (fish*) OR (halibut) OR (herring) OR (lobster*) OR (mackerel) OR (mollusc*) OR (mollusk*) OR (mussel*) OR (oyster*) OR (pollock) OR (prawn*) OR (salmon) OR (sardine) OR (scallop*) OR (shellfish) OR (shrimp*) OR (trout) OR (tuna) OR (hake) OR (crayfish) OR (bivalve*) OR (carp) OR (caviar) OR (squid) OR (cuttlefish) OR (cockle) OR (cockles) OR (snail) OR (eel) OR (sturgeon) OR (vegetable*) OR (produce) OR (“germinated seed”) OR (“green salad”) OR (“leafy green”) OR (“leafy greens”) OR (“mixed salad”) OR (“mixed vegetable”) OR (“pre-cut salad”) OR (“vegetable mix”) OR (fungi) OR (herb*) OR (lettuce) OR (mushroom*) OR (salad*) OR (spinach) OR (sprout*) OR (veggie*) OR (“raw produc”) OR (“frozen produc”) OR (microgreens) OR (avocado*) OR (salad*) OR (tomato*) OR (guacamole*) OR (taboulé) OR (pea) OR (peas) OR (bean) OR (beans) OR (chickpea*) OR (sprout*) OR (carrot) OR (carrots) OR (broccoli*) OR (beetroot*) OR (corn) OR (lentil*) OR (cucumber*) OR (legume*) OR (“dried seed”) OR (“dry seed”) OR (nut*) OR (oilseed*) OR (spice*) OR (pepper) OR (cinnamon) OR (turmeric) OR (cumin) OR (oregano) OR (nutmeg) OR (rosemary) OR (saffron) OR (basil) OR (garlic) OR (pulses) OR (almond) OR (sesame) OR (grain*) OR (bakery) OR (bread*) OR (cake*) OR (cereal*) OR (confectionary) OR (flakes) OR (flour) OR (maize) OR (pastries) OR (pastry) OR (rice) OR (seed*) OR (wheat) OR (fruit*) OR (“fruit mix”) OR (“fruit salad”) OR (“mixed fruit”) OR (“sliced fruit”) OR (“stone fruit”) OR (berries) OR (berry) OR (citrus*) OR (drupe*) OR (pome*) OR (apple*) OR (banana*) OR (melon*) OR (peach*) OR (fat) OR (oil*) OR (sugar*) OR (syrup*) OR (honey) OR (chocolate))

AND NOT

((“in vitro”) OR (“in-vitro”) OR (“challenge study”) OR (“essential oil”) OR (antimicrobial*) OR (attribution) OR (biofilm*) OR (“plant extract”) OR (“extracts”) OR (feed) OR (livestock) OR (sanitiser) OR (sanitizer) OR (spiked) OR (“feed supplement”))

String #3

((“microbial quality”) OR (“microbial safety”) OR (“microbiological quality”) OR (“microbiological safety”) OR (analyses) OR (analysis) OR (concentration) OR (contamination) OR (count*) OR (detection) OR (enumeration) OR (incidence) OR (investigation) OR (occurrence) OR (presence) OR (prevalence) OR (sampling) OR (survey))

AND

((Bacillus cereus) OR (“B. cereus”) OR (Clostridium perfringens) OR (“C. perfringens”) OR (STEC) OR (VTEC) OR (EHEC) OR (((Escherichia coli) OR (“E. coli”)) AND ((pathogenic) OR (shiga*) OR (verocytotoxi*) OR (enterohaemorrhagic) OR (enterohemorrhagic) OR (O157) OR (O157:H7) OR (O26:H11) OR (O145:H28) OR (O103:H2) OR (O111:H8) OR (O104:H4))) OR (Listeria monocytogenes) OR (“L. monocytogenes”) OR (Staphylococcus aureus) OR (“S. aureus”) OR (Yersinia enterocolitica) OR (“Y. enterocolitica”) OR (Campylobacter) OR (“C. jejuni”) OR (“C. coli”) OR (Salmonella) OR (Cryptosporidium) OR (“C. parvum”) OR (“C. hominis”) OR (Giardia) OR (“G. duodenalis”) OR (“G. intestinalis”) OR (“G. cuniculus”) OR (“G. meleagridis”) OR (“G. ubiquitum”) OR (“G. canis”) OR (“G. felis”) OR (“G. muris”) OR (“G. viatorum”) OR (Toxoplasma) OR (“T. gondii”) OR (“hepatitis A”) OR (“hepatitis E”) OR (HAV) OR (HEV) OR (norovirus) OR (norwalk))

AND

((meal) OR (meals) OR (food) OR (foods) OR (“buffet meal”) OR (“complex food”) OR (“frozen meal”) OR (multi-ingredient) OR (“multi ingredient”) OR (“probiotic drink”) OR (ready-to-eat) OR (RTE) OR (“ready meal”) OR (“ready prepared”) OR (“ready to eat”) OR (“sous vide”) OR (coleslaw) OR (composite*) OR (convenience) OR (cured) OR (dip) OR (dips) OR (dish) OR (dishes) OR (dressing*) OR (dumpling*) OR (fermented) OR (filling) OR (gravy) OR (hummus) OR (jam*) OR (kebab) OR (macerated) OR (marinad*) OR (marinate*) OR (mayonnaise) OR (pasta) OR (pizza) OR (pickled) OR (preserved) OR (pudding*) OR (puree*) OR (salsa) OR (salsas) OR (salted) OR (sandwich*) OR (sashimi) OR (ceviche) OR (sauce*) OR (smoked) OR (snack) OR (snacks) OR (soup) OR (soups) OR (stew*) OR (surimi) OR (sushi) OR (tofu*) OR (topping*) OR (vegan) OR (vegetarian) OR (chowder) OR (tahini))

AND NOT

((“in vitro”) OR (“in-vitro”) OR (“challenge study”) OR (“essential oil”) OR (antimicrobial*) OR (attribution) OR (biofilm*) OR (“plant extract”) OR (“extracts”) OR (feed) OR (livestock) OR (sanitiser) OR (sanitizer) OR (spiked) OR (“feed supplement”))

Filter mechanisms to be applied:

i. Year of publication (not date of database insertion)

Filter by ‘year’ (SciELO only filters by year of publication)

[or in the query string, add: AND year_cluster:("YYYY")]

ii. Type of publication (primary research articles and reviews)

Filter by document types ‘Article’ and ‘Review’

[or in the query string, add: AND type:("research-article" OR "review-article")]

Annex 2: PRISMA chart template

Description: Template of the PRISMA chart to be used to register the flow of literature records along the different phases of the systematic review linked to the PIF database. For every systematic review, three BibTeX files containing records post-deduplication, post-eligibility assessment and post-insertion will be uploaded on the Zenodo community.

Annex 3: PIF categorisation system of detection and enumeration methods for bacteria

Description: Categorisation structure implemented in the PIF database for the essays related to detection and enumeration of bacteria.

Detection (all techniques **involving enrichment**):

Agent	Type of detection essay	Detection essay
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Culture	N/S BacillusSelective MYP
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immuno	N/S
	N/S	
<i>Campylobacter</i>	Culture	N/S Campy-BAP CampylobacterSelective CCA Columbia ExeterSelective FAO ISO 10272-1:1995 ISO 10272-1:2006 mCCDA Preston+Virion NMKL 119 PHLS F21
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immuno	N/S VIDAS CAM
	N/S	
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	Culture	N/S
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immuno	N/S
	N/S	

<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Culture	N/S
		AFNOR BRD 07/4-09/98
		APHA 2001
		FSIS-USDA
		I+ALOA
		I+ALOA+ListeriaSelective
		I+ALOA+Oxford
		I+Chromogenic
		I+II+ALOA
		I+II+ALOA+Oxford
		I+II+Chromogenic
		I+II+ListeriaSelective
		I+II+ListeriaSelective/Oxford
		I+II+Oxford
		I+II+Oxford/PALCAM
		I+II+PALCAM
		I+II+RAPID
		I+ListeriaSelective
		I+ListeriaSelective/PALCAM
		I+LPM/Blood
		I+Oxford
		I+Oxford/PALCAM
		I+PALCAM
IMS+ListeriaSelective		
IMS+Oxford		
IMS+PALCAM		
IMS+PALCAM/Oxford		
ISO 11290-1		
ISO 11290-1:1996		
ISO 11290-1:2004		
NMKL 136		
PHLS F19		
DNA	N/S	
	IMS+PCR	
	iQ-Check	
	PCR	
Immuno	N/S	
	AFNOR BIO 12/11-03/04	
	VIDAS LMO2	
N/S		

<i>Salmonella</i>	Culture	N/S
		AOAC 1998
		APHA 2001
		BS EN 12824:1998
		DIASSALM+Rambach
		IDF Standard 93B
		IMS+HE/XLD
		IMS+XLD
		ISO 6579:1993
		ISO 6579:2002
		ISO 6579:2004
		ISO 6579:2007
		ISO 6785:2001
		NF V08-052
		NMLK 71
		PHLS F13
		RAPIDCapsule+Agar
		RV/SC+BG
		RV/SC+BG/BS
		RV/SC+BG/HE
		RV/SC+BG/SS
		RV/SC+BG/XLD
		RV/SC+BS/SS
		RV/SC+HE
		RV/SC+HE/SS/XLD
		RV/SC+Rambach
		RV/SC+XLD
		RV/TT+BG
		RV/TT+BG/BS/XLD
		RV/TT+BG/XLD
		RV/TT+BS/HE/XLD
		RV/TT+Chromogenic
		RV/TT+HE/SS
		RV/TT+HE/XLD
		RV/TT+McConkey/XLD
		RV/TT+Rambach/XLD
		RV/TT+XLD
		RV+BG
		RV+BG/HE
		RV+BG/HE/XLD
		RV+BG/XLD
		RV+Chromogenic
		RV+Rambach
		RV+SS
		RV+XLD
		SC/TT+BG/HE/XLD
		SC/TT+BG/SS/XLD
		SC/TT+XLD
		SC+BG/BS
		SC+BS
		SC+BS/SS
		SC+Chromogenic
		SC+Rambach

		SC+SS SC+XLD Standard M19 TT+BG/BS/XLD TT+HE TT+McConkey/XLD TT+SS TT+XLD
	DNA	N/S iQ-Check PCR
	Immuno	N/S ELISA VIDAS SLM
	N/S	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Culture	N/S ISO 6888-2:1999 APHA 1992 MHB+Chromogenic MHB+MRSA-ID MHB+PHMB+MRSA-ID MHB+TSB+Chromogenic
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immuno	N/S
	N/S	
Shiga toxin producing <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Culture	N/S APHA 2001 BAM BGB+SMAC Biolog MicroStation BPW+CT-SMAC IMS+Chromogenic IMS+CT-SMAC ISO 16654:2001 mEC+CT-SMAC mEC+SMAC PHLS F17 TSB+Chromogenic TSB+CT-SMAC TSB+SMAC
	DNA	N/S GeneDisc IMS+PCR iQ-Check ISO/TS 13136:2012 PCR

	Immuno	N/S AFNOR BIO 12/8-07/00 ISO 16654:2001 LatexTest VIDAS-ECO VIDAS-ICE
	N/S	
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	Culture	N/S CIN ISO 10273:1994 ISO 10273:2003 ITC+CIN PBS+CIN PBSS+CIN TPW+CIN TSB+BOS+CIN TSB+CIN YersiniaBroth+CIN
	DNA	N/S NMKL 163 PCR
	Immuno	N/S ELISA
	N/S	

Abbreviations

General terms: N/S: not specified; A+B: Combination of culturing in enrichment broth A and plating in agar B; A/B+C/D: Combination of culturing in enrichment broths A+B and plating in agar C+D; ISO: International Organization for Standardization Standard Methods; NMKL: Nordic-Baltic Committee on Food Analysis Standard Methods; PHLS: Public Health Laboratory Service/ Health Protection Agency Standard Methods; AFNOR: Association Française de Normalisation Standard Methods; APHA: American Public Health Association Standard Methods; AOAC: Association of Official Analytical Chemists Standard Methods; BS EN: British Standard (BS) adaptation of a European Norm (EN); IDF: International Dairy Federation Standards; NF: French Standard (Norme Française); ISO/TS: ISO Technical Specification; **B. cereus:** Bacillus Selective: Bacillus cereus Selective Agar; MYP: Mannitol Egg Yolk Agar; **Campylobacter:** Campy-BAP: Campylobacter Blood Agar; Campylobacter Selective: Campylobacter Selective Agar; CCA: Campy-Cefex Agar; Columbia: Columbia Blood Agar; Exeter Selective: Exeter Campylobacter Selective Broth; FAO: Campylobacter detection method from the Manual of Food Quality Control by the United Nations' Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO); mCCDA: Modified Charcoal Cefoperazone. Deoxycholate Agar; Preston: Preston broth; Virion: Virion plates (Mueller Hinton agar+Bacto agar+5% of defibrinated horse blood); VIDAS CAM: Detection of Campylobacter by Enzyme Linked Fluorescent Assay using a VIDAS instrument; **L. monocytogenes:** FSIS-USDA: United States Department of Agriculture, Food Safety and Inspection Service procedure for detection/enumeration of *L. monocytogenes*; I+A: First enrichment + plating in agar A; I+A+B or I+A/B: First enrichment + plating in agar A+B; I+II+A: First enrichment + second enrichment + plating in agar A; I+II+A/B: First enrichment + second enrichment + plating in agar A+B; ALOA: Chromogenic Agar Listeria Ottaviani & Agosti; Listeria Selective: Listeria Selective Agar; Oxford: Listeria Oxford Agar; Chromogenic: Chromogenic Agar; PALCAM: Polymyxin Acriflavin Lithium-chloride Cefotaxime Esculin Mannitol (PALCAM) Listeria Selective Agar; RAPID: RAPID L.mono agar; LPM: Lithium Chloride-Phenylethanol-Moxalactam (LPM) Agar; Blood: Blood Agar; IMS: immunomagnetic separation; iQ-Check: iQ-Check PCR Detection Kit; VIDAS LMO2: Detection of *L. monocytogenes* by Enzyme Linked Fluorescent Assay using a VIDAS instrument; **Salmonella:** DIASSALM: Diagnostic Semi Solid Salmonella Agar; Rambach: Rambach Chromogenic Agar; IMS: immunomagnetic separation; HE: Hektoen Enteric Agar; XLD: Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate (XLD) Agar; RAPID Capsule+Agar: RAPID 'Salmonella Capsule pre-enrichment + agar plating; RV: Rappaport Vassiliadis Salmonella Broth; SC: Selenite Cystine broth; BG: Brilliant Green Agar; BS: Bismuth Sulfite Agar; SS: Salmonella Shigella Agar; TT: Tetrathionate Broth; Chromogenic: Chromogenic Agar; McConkey: MacConkey Agar; Standard M19: Salmonella spp. detection standard method from the Hellenic Army's Manual of Laboratory Examination

Techniques for Foods, Beverages and Water; ELISA: Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; VIDAS SLM: Detection of Salmonella by Enzyme Linked Fluorescent Assay using a VIDAS instrument; **S. aureus**: MHB: Mueller-Hinton Broth; Chromogenic: Chromogenic Agar; MRSA-ID: Methicillin-Resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) chromogenic agar; PHMB: Polyhexamethylene biguanide supplement; TSB: Tryptic Soy Broth; **E.coli**: BAM: E.coli detection methods of the Bacteriological Analytical Manual by the United States Food and Drug Administration (US FDA); BGB: Brilliant Green Bile Broth; SMAC: Sorbitol MacConkey Agar; Biolog MicroStation: Biolog's microbiological biochemistry system for E.coli identification; BPW: Buffered Peptone Water; CT-SMAC: Cefixime-Tellurite Sorbitol MacConkey Agar; mEC: Modified E. coli Broth; TSB: Tryptic Soy Broth; Chromogenic: Chromogenic Agar; GeneDisc: GeneDisc microbiological quantitative PCR system; IMS: immunomagnetic separation; iQ-Check: iQ-Check PCR Detection Kit; LatexTest: Latex agglutination test; VIDAS-ECO: Detection of E. coli O157 by Enzyme Linked Fluorescent Assay using a VIDAS instrument; VIDAS-ICE: Selective concentration of E. coli O157 detected by VIDAS-ECO using a VIDAS instrument; **Y. enterocolitica**: CIN: Cefsulodin-Irgasan-Novobiocin (CIN) Agar; ITC: Irgasan Ticarcillin Chlorate (ITC) Broth; PBS: Phosphate-Buffered Saline; PBSS: Phosphate-Buffered Saline swabs (as transport medium); TPW: Tris-buffered peptone water; TSB: Tryptic Soy Broth; BOS: Bile Oxalate Sorbose Broth; YersiniaBroth: Yersinia selective enrichment broth.

Enumeration (direct plating):

Agent	Type of enumeration essay	Enumeration essay
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Culture	N/S MPN MYP APHA 2001 ISO 7932:1993 ISO 7932:1997 ISO 7932:2004 PHLS F15 PEMBA BacillusSelective
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immunological	N/S
	N/S	
<i>Campylobacter</i>	Culture	N/S MPN CampyCefex CCDA mCCDA ISO 10272-2:2006
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immunological	N/S
	N/S	

<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	Culture	N/S MPN ISO 7937:2004 ISO 15213:2003 ISO 7937:1997 BS 5763-9:1993 PHLS F14 TSC Sulfite-polymyxin-sulfadiazine Perfringens APHA 2001 Trypticase-sulfite-neomycin Lactose-Sulfite Wilson-Blair AOAC 1998
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immunological	N/S
	N/S	
	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Culture
DNA		N/S PCR
Immunological		N/S
N/S		
<i>Salmonella</i>		Culture
	DNA	N/S PCR
	Immunological	N/S
	N/S	

<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Culture	N/S MPN AOAC 1998 APHA 1992 APHA 2001 BP BP+EY BP+RabbitPlasma Columbia+RabbitPlasma IDF 145A:1997 ISO 6888-1:1999 ISO 6888-1:2003 ISO 6888-2:1999 ISO 6888-2:2003 ISO 6888-3:2003 KRANEP MS NMKL 66 Petrifilm PHLS F12	
	DNA	N/S PCR	
	Immunological	N/S VIDAS-SET	
	N/S		
	Shiga toxin producing <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Culture	N/S MPN
		DNA	N/S PCR
		Immunological	N/S
		N/S	
	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	Culture	N/S MPN
		DNA	N/S PCR
Immunological		N/S	
N/S			

Abbreviations

General terms: N/S: not specified; MPN: Most Probable Number; A+B: Combination of culturing in enrichment broth A and plating in agar B or Medium A with added supplement B; A/B+C/D: Combination of culturing in enrichment broths A+B and plating in agar C+D; APHA: American Public Health Association Standard Methods; ISO: International Organization for Standardization Standard Methods; PHLS: Public Health Laboratory Service/ Health Protection Agency Standard Methods; BS: British Standard; AOAC: Association of Official Analytical Chemists Standard Methods; IDF: International Dairy Federation Standards; NMKL: Nordic-Baltic Committee on Food Analysis Standard Methods; **B. cereus:** MYP: Mannitol Egg Yolk Agar; PEMBA: Polymyxin Pyruvate Egg-yolk Mannitol Bromothymol-blue Agar (PEMBA); BacillusSelective: Bacillus cereus Selective Agar; **Campylobacter:** CampyCefex: Campy Cefex Agar; CCDA: Charcoal Cefoperozone Deoxycholate Agar (CCDA); mCCDA: Modified Charcoal Cefoperazone. Deoxycholate Agar; **Clostridium:** TSC: Tryptose Sulfite Cycloserine Agar; Sulfite-polymyxin-sulfadiazine: Sulfite Polymyxin Sulfadiazine (SPS) Agar; Perfringens: Perfringens Agar (or Oleandomycin Polymyxin Sulphadiazine Perfringens (OPSP) Agar); Trypticase-sulfite-neomycin: Trypticase Sulfite Neomycin (TSN) Agar; Lactose-Sulfite: Lactose Sulfite Broth; Wilson-Blair: Wilson Blair Agar; **L. monocytogenes:** ListeriaSelective: Listeria Selective Agar; Oxford: Listeria Oxford Agar; PALCAM: Polymyxin Acriflavin Lithium-chloride Ceftazidime Esculin Mannitol (PALCAM) Listeria Selective Agar; ALOA: Chromogenic Agar Listeria Ottaviani & Agosti; FSIS-USDA: United States Department of

Agriculture, Food Safety and Inspection Service procedure for detection/enumeration of *L. monocytogenes*; Chromogenic: Chromogenic Agar; FDA: US Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) methods for detection/enumeration of *L. monocytogenes*; **S. aureus**: BP: Baird Parker Agar; EY: Egg Yolk Tellurite Emulsion Supplement; Rabbit Plasma: Rabbit Plasma Fibrinogen (RPF) Supplement; Columbia: Columbia Blood Agar; KRANEP: Kalium-Rhodanid Actidione Natriumazid Eigelb Pyruvate (KRANEP) Agar; MS: Mannitol Salt (MSA) Agar; Petrifilm: 3M Petrifilm™ Staph express count system for enumeration of *S. aureus*; VIDAS-SET: VIDAS SET2 test for detection of Staphylococcal Enterotoxins using a VIDAS instrument.

Annex 4: PIF food categorisation system

Description: Food categorisation structure implemented in the PIF database for data extraction related to bacteria, parasites and viruses

Food category	Food subcategory	Food class	Food subclass (Specie or Heat treated)	Food subclass 2 (Specie)	
Beverages	CoffeeTea				
	Juices				
	SoftDrink				
	Water				
	TapWater				
	OtherWater	Specify Water:			
Composite	UndefinedB				
	RTE	Cooked			
	Dishes	Raw			
	Sandwich	NA			
	FastFood				
Dairy	UndefinedC				
	Cheese	Hard	Pasteurised	Bovine	
		Semi-hard	Raw	Ovine	
		Soft	NA	Caprine	
		NA		Camel	
				Mixed	
	Fats	Fermented			NA
		Powder			
		Whey			
		Milk	Pasteurised	Bovine	
Raw			Ovine		
NA	Caprine				
	Camel				
	Donkey				
UndefinedD	Pasteurised	Bovine			
	Raw	Ovine			
	NA	Caprine			
		Donkey			
		Mixed			
Eggs	NA	NA			
	Eggs	Pasteurised			
	EggProducts	Raw			
		Cooked			
Fruits	Dried	NA			
	Drupes	Pre-cut			
	Citrus	NA			
	Berries				

	Pome			
	ProcessedF			
	UndefinedF			
Grains	Bread			
	CakesPastries			
	Cereals	Cooked		
	Pasta	NA		
	UndefinedG			
Legumes	DrySeeds			
	Nuts			
	OilSeeds			
	Legumes	Cooked		
	Spices	Dried		
	ProcessedL	Fermented		
	UndefinedL	NA		
Meat	Beef	Cooked		
	Chicken	Mince		
	Pork	Pre-cut		
	UndefinedM	NA		
	ProcMeat	Cooked	Bovine	
		Cured	Ovine	
		Raw	Pork	
		NA	Poultry	
			Mixed	
			NA	
	Game	Cooked	Deer	
		Mince	Wild boar	
		Pre-cut	Other	
NA		NA		
OtherMeats	Cooked	Caprine		
	Mince	Equine		
	Pre-cut	Ovine		
	NA	Rabbit		
		Other		
		NA		
OtherPoultry	Cooked	Duck		
	Mince	Turkey		
	Pre-cut	Other		
	NA	NA		
Oils				
Seafood	Crustaceans	Fresh	Shrimp	
		Pre-cut	Crab	
		Cooked	Other	
		NA	NA	
	Fish	Fresh		
		Pre-cut		
		Cooked		
	UndefinedS	NA		
	Molluscs	Fresh	Cockles	
Pre-cut		Mussels		
Cooked		Oysters		
NA		Scallops		
		Clams		

		Other NA
	ProcessedS	Dry Marinated Smoked NA
Sugars		
Vegetables	AromaticHerbs	Dried
	Fungi	Minimally
	Roots	Cooked
	Sprouts	NA
	Fresh	Minimally NA
	VegProducts	Dried Minimally Fermented Cooked NA

Abbreviations

General terms: NA: Not available; Cooked: Foods subjected to a heat treatment for the purpose of consumption; Raw: Foods that have not been subjected to any type of heat treatment; Pasteurised: Foods subjected to a pasteurization heat treatment for the purpose of preservation; Dried: Foods subjected to a drying (removal of moisture) process for the purpose of preservation; Fermented: Foods subjected to fermentation by microorganisms for the purpose of preservation; Mince: Foods subjected to grinding or chopping; Pre-cut: Food subjected to cutting or jointing before packaging; Cured: Foods subjected to food preservation by the addition of a combination of salt and other ingredients, with partial drying and biological maturation; Fresh: Foods that have not been subjected to any type of processing; Marinated: Foods subjected to a step of soaking in a seasoned liquid, for the purpose of flavouring (usually before cooking); Smoked: Foods subjected to exposure to the smoke of burning wood for the purpose of flavouring, cooking and/or preservation; Minimally: Foods subjected to minimal processing, usually by just washing the surface with water or washing solutions, to remove superficial contamination or dirt; **Beverages:** CoffeeTea: Coffee and tea products/ingredients; Juices: Juice/nectar drinks or ingredients; Water: Bottled drinking water; TapWater: Drinking water from the tap/distribution network; OtherWater: Other types of drinking water; SpecifyWater: Specify type of other drinking water; UndefinedB: Undefined beverages that do not fit the other 'Beverages' subcategories; **Composite:** RTE: Ready-to-eats foods; FastFood: Fast food-type of composite foods; Dishes: Composite or multi-ingredient dishes; Sandwich: Sandwich-type stuffed bread-like cereal products; UndefinedC: Undefined composite foods that do not fit the other 'Composite' subcategories; **Dairy:** Fats: Fats obtained from dairy; Fermented: Fermented milk and dairy products; Powder: Milk and dairy powders and concentrates; UndefinedD: Undefined dairy that do not fit the other 'Dairy' subcategories; **Eggs:** EggProducts: Food products/ingredients/derivatives obtained from eggs; **Fruits:** ProcessedF: Fruits subjected to at least one step of processing (ex.: freezing, pureeing, fermenting, etc.); UndefinedF: Undefined fruits that do not fit the other 'Fruits' subcategories; **Grains:** CakesPastries: Cakes, pastries and other fine-bakery products; UndefinedG: Undefined grains that do not fit the other 'Grains' subcategories; **Legumes:** DrySeeds: Dried seeds (pulses) from any type of legumes; OilSeeds: Seeds grown primarily for the production of edible oils; ProcessedL: Legumes subjected to at least one step of processing (ex.: oil extraction, fermenting, etc.); UndefinedL: Undefined legumes that do not fit the other 'Legumes' subcategories; **Meat:** UndefinedM: Undefined meat that do not fit the other 'Meat' subcategories; ProcMeat: Meat products subjected to at least one step of processing (ex.: sausages); Game: Meat from game animals; OtherMeats: Meats from animals other than cattle, pork or poultry; OtherPoultry: Meats from poultry other than chicken; **Seafood:** UndefinedS: Undefined seafood that do not fit the other 'Seafood' subcategories; ProcessedS: Seafood products subjected to at least one step of processing (ex.: smoked salmon); **Vegetables:** Fresh: Non-processed fresh vegetables; VegProducts: Vegetable products subjected to at least one step of processing (ex.: frozen broccoli).

Annex 5: PIF categorisation system of detection, enumeration, identification and infectivity methods for viruses

Description: Categorisation structure implemented in the PIF database for the essays related to detection, enumeration, identification and infectivity determination for viruses.

Detection:

Agent	Type of detection essay	Detection essay	Immuno-globulin class
Hepatitis A (HAV)	Molecular	Conventional RT-PCR Nested-RT PCR (nPCR) Quantitative-PCR or real time (RT-qPCR) Semi-nested RT PCR Multiplex PCR Digital PCR RT-dPCR ISO/TS 15216:2013 ISO 15216:2017 ISO 15216:2019 Combination Other	
	Other	Specify:	
Hepatitis E (HEV)	Molecular	Conventional RT-PCR Quantitative-PCR or real time (RT-qPCR) LAMP (reverse transcription-LAMP assay) Multiplex PCR Digital PCR RT-dPCR Other	
	Immuno	Western Blot ELISA or EIA (enzyme immunoassay)	IgM IgG IgA
	Other	Specify:	
Norovirus	Molecular	Conventional RT-PCR Nested-RT PCR (nPCR) Quantitative-PCR or real time (RT-qPCR) Semi-nested RT PCR Multiplex PCR Digital PCR RT-dPCR ISO/TS 15216:2013 ISO 15216:2017 ISO 15216:2019 Combination Other	
	Other	Specify:	

Enumeration:

Agent	Type of enumeration essay	Enumeration essay
Hepatitis A (HAV)	Quantitative-PCR real time (qPCR)	
	Reference PCR methods	ISO/TS 15216:2013 ISO 15216:2017 ISO 15216:2019
	Digital PCR qPCR	
	Multiplex qPCR	
	PCR-NPP	
	Other	Specify:
	Hepatitis E (HEV)	Quantitative-PCR or real time (qPCR)
LAMP (reverse transcription-LAMP assay)		
Digital PCR RT-qPCR		
Multiplex RT-qPCR		
PCR-NPP		
Other		Specify:
Norovirus	Quantitative-PCR real time (qPCR)	
	Reference PCR methods	ISO/TS 15216:2013 ISO 15216:2017 ISO 15216:2019
	Digital PCR qPCR	
	Multiplex qPCR	
	PCR-NPP	
	Other	Specify:

Identification:

Agent	Type of identification essay	Identification essay
Hepatitis A (HAV)	WGS	
	NGS	
	Other	Specify:
Hepatitis E (HEV)	WGS	
	NGS	
	Other	Specify:
Norovirus	WGS	
	NGS	
	Other	Specify:

Annex 6: PIF categorisation system of sample preparation, detection, enumeration, identification and infectivity methods for parasites

Description: Categorisation structure implemented in the PIF database for the essays related to sample preparation, detection, enumeration, identification and infectivity determination for parasites.

Sample preparation:

Agent	Sample preparation essay	Other sample preparation essay
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	Centrifugation	
	Sequence based Magnetic capture (for PCR)	
	Artificial digestion (trypsin or pepsin or glycin)	
	Percoll gradients	
	Flocculation with (Fe ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ +Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃)	
	Flotation	
	LMS (lectin)	
	Filtration	
	Flotation in sucrose	
	Magnetic based Capture	
Other		Specify:
<i>Giardia</i>	Immunomagnetic separation (IMS) as ISO 18744	
	Immunomagnetic separation (IMS) non precise	
	Centrifugation+IMS	
	Elution+concentration+IMS	
	Flow cytometry	
	Centrifugation	
	Bailenger concentration method	
	Umeche technic	
	Stomaching or stomaching with glycin	
	Washing or washing+tween	
	Formol-ether	
Other		Specify:

<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Centrifugation Surface elution centrifugation Elution+concentration Concentrator Flotation Immunomagnetic separation (IMS) as ISO 18744 Immunomagnetic separation (IMS) as UUtaker et al,2015 Immonomagnetic separation (IMS) not referenced Microfiltration Centrifugation+IMS Elution+concentration+IMS MIFC Merthiolate iodine-formaldehyde concentration Bailenger method Sucrose gradient Laberge Gradient zinc Gradient phycol Gradient percoll Flow cytometry Other	Specify:
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Prevalence:

Agent	Type of detection essay	Detection essay	Cutoff/ molecular target
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	Immuno	ELISA	Specify cutoff:
		Indirect ELISA	
		MAT (modified agglutination assay) Other	
	Microscopy	Stain Giemsa or haemotoxylin and eosin or wright giemsa	
		IHC (enzymes)	
		Fluorescent-conjugated antibodies	
Autofluorescence Other			
Molecular	Nested PCR (nPCR) Quantitative Real-time PCR (qPCR)	PCR target B1 gene	PCR target 529 bp repeat elements SAG-2 Other
		Conventional PCR	
		Semi-nested PCR	
	LAMP (Loop-mediated isothermal amplification) LAMP+lateral flow dipstick chromatographic detection		

	Combination	ELISA+MAT ELISA+MAT+PCR CCqPCR (target 529b) PMA-qPCR (Propidium Monoazide-based qPCR) Other		
	Bioassay	Cat bioessay Mouse bioessay		
	Other	Specify:		
<i>Giardia</i>	Immuno	ELISA or EIAS (immunoassays or immunosorbent assays) IFM+ELISA IFA or IFT or DFA or IFM (immunofluorescent assays) Rapid immunochromatographic assays (dipsticks) Other	Specify cutoff:	
	Microscopy	Trichrome staining Iodine/iron (lugol)/hematoxylin/giemsa Saline wet mount Direct smear DIC microscopy (differential interference contrast) Modified Zn staining Other		
	Molecular	Conventional PCR	Triosephosphate isomerase (tpi) Glutamate deshydrogenase (gdh) ARN18S or SSU rRNA gene Beta-giardin (bg) Multilocus Other	
		PCR-RFLP	Triosephosphate isomerase (tpi) ARN18S or SSU rRNA gene Beta-giardin (bg) Other	
Nested PCR (nPCR) Semi-nested		Triosephosphate isomerase (tpi) Glutamate deshydrogenase (gdh) ARN18S or SSU rRNA gene Beta-giardin (bg) Other		
Quantitative-PCR real time (PCR, qPCR) Real-time PCR		ARN18S or SSU rRNA gene Other		

		MicroRNA-based method Multiplex-tandem PCR	
	Reference methods	ISO 18744:2016 (IMS+IFM) (produce) : Centrifugation+IMS-CG+IFA NF T90-455 (AFNOR 2001) (IMSCG+IFA) (water) ISO 15553: 2006 (water) 1623 USEPA: 2001 (water) ICR-USEPA: 1995 (water) (filtration+IMS+IFA) 1623 USEPA : 2005 (water) (filtration+IMS+IFA)	
	Other	Specify:	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Immuno	ELISA or EIAS (immunoassays or immunosorbent assays) IFM+ELISA IFA or IFT or DFA or IFM (immunofluorescent assays) Rapid immunochromatographic assays (dipsticks) Other	Specify cutoff:
	Microscopy	Safranin-methylen-blue Kinyoun Ziehl-Neelsen Lugol or iodure and lugol+zn staining Modified Zn staining Direct smear Dimethyl sulfoxide-carbol fuchsin-(Heine) Other	
	Molecular	Conventional PCR	ARN 18S or SSU rRNA COWP SSP70 (not referenced) Other or Not specified PCR as Hohweyer 2016 (SSP70)
		Nested-PCR	GP60
		Semi-nested PCR	ARN 18S or SSU rRNA COWP Other or Not specified
		Quantitative-PCR real time PCR	ARN 18S or SSU rRNA SSP70 Other or Not specified
		Multiplex PCR	
		Combination	IFM+PCR IMS+PCR Other combination

Reference methods	ISO 18744 (2016) NF T90-455 (AFNOR 2001) ISO 15553 (2006) Drinking water inspectorate (2005) UUtaker et al (2015) (IMS+BFM) 1623 USEPA (2001) (water) 1623 USEPA (2005) (water filtration/IMS+IFA) ICR-USEPA 1995 (water filtration/IMS-CG+IFA)
Other	Specify:

Enumeration:

Agent	Type of enumeration essay	Enumeration essay	Molecular target
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	Molecular	Quantitative-PCR real time (qPCR)	PCR target B1 gene PCR target 529 bp repeat elements SAG-2 Other
		Nested-PCR quantitative (nPCR)	PCR target B1 gene PCR target 529 bp repeat elements SAG2 Other target
		Other	Specify:
<i>Giardia</i>	Immuno	IFA or IFT or DFA or IFM (immunofluorescent assays) ELISA or EIAS (immunoassays or immunosorbent assays) Rapid immunochromatographic assays (dipsticks) IFM+ELISA Other	
	Microscopy	Trichrome staining Iodine/iron (lugol)/hematoxylin/giemsa Saline wet mount Direct smear DIC microscopy (differential interference contrast) Modified Zn staining Other	

	Molecular	Quantitative-PCR real time (qPCR)	ARN18S or SSU rRNA gene Other
		Other	
	Other	Specify:	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Immuno	ELISA or EIAS (immunoassays or immunosorbent assays) IFM+ELISA	Specify cutoff
		IFA or IFT or DFA or IFM (immunofluorescent assays) Rapid immunochromatographic assays (dipsticks) Other	
	Microscopy	Safranin-methylen-blue Kinyoun Ziehl-Neelsen Lugol or iodure and lugol+zn staining Modified Zn staining Direct smear Dimethyl sulfoxide-carbol fuchsin-(Heine) Other or not specified	
	Molecular	Quantitative-PCR or real time (qPCR)	ARN 18S or SSU rRNA SSP70 Other or Not specified
		Other	
	Other	Specify:	

Identification:

Agent	Type of identification essay	Identification essay	Molecular target
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	Enzymatic	Multilocus enzyme electrophoresis Other	
	Molecular	WGS Clade and haplogroups MLST Haplogroups PCR-RFLP ToxoDB genotype Microsatellite typing 15 MicroSatellites Combination Other	
	Other	Specify:	

<i>Giardia</i>	Molecular (genotyping)	PCR Sequencing analysis PCR-RFLP	Triosephosphate isomerase (tpi) Glutamate deshydrogenase (gdh) ARN18S or SSU rRNA gene Beta-giardin(bg) Other
	Other	Specify: WGS Multilocus genotyping tool RAPD (18S) FISH (Fluorescent in situ hybridization)	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Molecular	High Resolution Melt (HRM) Nested PCR-RFLP MLST multilocus gene sequencing/typing MLST multilocus fragment typing tools 18S DNA sequencing HSP70 sequencing COWP sequencing Cp47 sequencing GP-60 gene sequencing T-rich gene fragment Serine repeat antigen RPGR MSC6-7 WGS Other	
	Other	Specify:	

Infectivity:

Agent	Type of infectivity essay	Infectivity essay class	Molecular target
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	Bioassay	Cat bioassay Mouse bioassay	
	Culture	Vero cell lines Liquid (fluid samples) Hep-2 cells Murine L20B fibroblasts Human foreskin fibroblasts Other	
	Molecular methods	RT-PCR or RT-qPCR	SporoSAG Act11 Other
	Other	Other	
	Excystation		
	Microscopy – Method based on morphology		

	Method based on physical properties (electrorotation)	
	Vital dye exclusion+PMA	
	Combination	CCqPCR (target 529b) PMA-qPCR (Propidium Monoazide-based qPCR)
	Other	Specify:
<i>Giardia</i>	Vital Dyes inclusion exclusion essays	
	Method based on physical properties (electrorotation)	
	Bioassay	Immunosuppressed mongolian gerbill model Other
	Excystation essay	
	Molecular methods	RT-PCR (reverse transcriptase PCR) Beta-giardin Other
		Duplex-PCR Other
	Combination	EMA/PMA+qPCR Other
	Other	Specify:
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Microscopy	Method based on morphology Other
	Method based on physical properties (electrorotation)	
	Vital dye inclusion/exclusion	
	Bioassay	Neonatal mouse model (Balbc or NMRI) Gnotobiotic pig model Immunosuppressed mongolian gerbill model
	Cell culture	HCP8 Caco-2 Other
	Excystation essay	
	Molecular methods	RT-PCR (reverse transcriptase PCR) HSP70 Other
		FISH (Fluorescent in situ hybridization) NASBA (Nucleic Acid Sequence Based Amplification)
	Combination	EMA/PMA+PCR ARN 18S or SSU rRNA COWP SSP70 Other

EMA/PMA+qPCR

ARN 18S or
SSU rRNA
SSP70
Other

Other

Specify:
